

BIOBUILD

Thermal Solutions for Green Buildings

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Technical, market codes, and certification strategies

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List of terms and definitions

Terms	Definition
EUROCODES	<p>Eurocodes are series of 10 European Technical Standards that provide a common approach to the structural design of buildings and other civil engineering works. Eurocodes help the European companies to be more competitive and increase safety in the construction industry.</p> <p>The Eurocodes cover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the basis of structural design (EN 1990). It is a pan-European building code that has superseded the older national building codes. Each country has now National Annexes to localize the contents of the Eurocodes; • the actions on structures (EN 1991); • the design of concrete (EN 1992), steel (EN 1993), composite steel and concrete (EN 1994), timber (EN 1995), masonry (EN 1996), and aluminium structures (EN 1999); • the geotechnical design (EN 1997); • the design, assessment, and retrofitting of structures for earthquake resistance (EN 1998).
Standardisation gap	Any need that cannot be covered, fully or partially, by an existing standard.
Opportunity	Any item such as a document, existing standards, standards under development, a workshop agreement or even a technological solution that can address a particular need and facilitate the process of pre-standardisation.
Standard	<p>Technical document designed to be used as a guide, a guideline, a definition or even a rule.</p> <p>https://www.cen.eu/work/endevelop/whatisen/pages/default.aspx</p>
Residential building	<p>Type of structure primarily designed and constructed to serve as a dwelling place for individuals and families. These buildings are intended for residential use and provide a place for people to live, sleep, and carry out their daily activities. Residential buildings are in various forms, sizes, and architectural styles.</p> <p>Common types of residential buildings.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-Family Homes: These are standalone houses designed to accommodate a single family or household. They often have their own yards or outdoor spaces and offer a high degree of privacy. Single-family homes are in various styles, from ranch-style to colonial, and can vary in size and layout. • Duplexes and Triplexes: Duplexes are residential buildings divided into two separate housing units, while triplexes have three units. Each unit typically has its own entrance and may share common walls. These are often used for small-scale multi-family living or as investment properties. • Townhouses: Townhouses are typically multi-story homes with shared walls between units. They form a row of homes and can vary in size from small to large. Townhouses often have communal amenities like shared green spaces or parking areas. • Apartment Buildings: Apartment buildings consist of multiple individual apartments within a single structure. They can range from low-rise buildings with a few stories to high-rise skyscrapers with many floors. Apartments may offer various amenities like fitness centres, laundry facilities, and communal spaces. • Condominiums (Condos): Condominiums are similar to apartments in structure but differ in ownership. Each condo unit is individually owned by the occupant, and common areas and amenities are shared and managed by a condominium association. Condo owners pay fees for maintenance and upkeep of these shared spaces.

Non-residential building	A building, or portion thereof, used for a purpose other than a dwelling.
Bio-based material	A material intentionally made from substances derived from living (or once-living) organisms. These materials are sometimes referred to as biomaterials, but this word also has another meaning. Strictly the definition could include many common materials such as wood and leather, but it typically refers to modern materials that have undergone more extensive processing. Unprocessed materials may be called biotic material. Bio-based materials or biomaterials fall under the broader category of bio-products or bio-based products, which includes materials, chemicals and energy derived from renewable biological resources. Bio-based materials are often biodegradable, but this is not always the case ¹ .
Nearly zero-emission building (NZEB)	A building that has a very high energy performance, with nearly zero or very low amount of energy required that should be covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby. According to the revised directive's (Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings (recast)), a zero emission building is defined as a building with a very high energy performance, very low amount of energy required and fully covered by energy from renewable sources and without on-site carbon emissions from fossil fuels. The ZEB requirement should apply as of 1 January 2030 to all new buildings, and as of 1 January 2027 to all new buildings occupied or owned by public authorities.
Temperature cycle	Variable temperature with a given amplitude and frequency EN ISO 7730:2005.
Greenhouse gas (GHG)	Any gas in the atmosphere which absorbs and re-emits heat. The main GHGs are water vapour, carbon dioxide (CO ₂), methane (CH ₄) and nitrous oxide (N ₂ O).
Carbon footprint	The sum of all GHG emissions of a given product, asset, or activity.
End-of-life carbon	Emissions which occur after a building or infrastructure project's lifetime – whether associated with deconstruction/demolition, transport from the site, waste processing, or disposal.

¹ BIOBASED MATERIALS, CURRAN, M. A. BIOBASED MATERIALS. Kirk-Othmer Encyclopaedia of Chemical Technology, ISBN: 9780471238966. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, NJ, 1-19, (2010).

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electro-technical Standardisation
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
EC	European Commission
EGD	European Green Deal
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration. A third-party verified report of the LCA results of a product.
EUROSTAT	EUROSTAT is the statistical office of the European Union, responsible for publishing high-quality Europe-wide statistics and indicators that enable comparisons between countries and regions.
EU	European Union
ISO	International Standardization Organization
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Currently, buildings in Europe account for 40% of energy use and about 95% of the binders used in wood-fibre composites are fossil-derived. Non-biobased materials (e.g., bricks, concrete, plastic, gypsum, glass and rock wool) have high environmental footprints, limited recycling possibilities and should be replaced with bio-based, sustainable materials.

BIOBUILD project, co-funded by the Horizon Europe programme, focuses on the use of bio-composites to develop non-toxic and zero-pollution building materials with an energy storage functionality. It will incorporate bio-based phase change materials (bioPCM) into solid wood, wood fibres and particles bound by plant oil resins, lignin, or fungal mycelia. The products will be fully recyclable and sustainable without toxic compounds.

The transition towards climate neutrality as set out in the European Green Deal (EGD) calls for innovative and rapid changes. The BIOBUILD project will pave the way to further achieve the EGD goals and speed up innovation in buildings, contributing to a wider use of bio-based materials and expanding the bio-based market to benefit civil society and the environment. The sustainable bio-based materials and technologies will potentially contribute to the imminent transition to decarbonisation in major industrial sectors.

BIOBUILD project aims to achieve the following main objectives:

- Incorporating the bioPCMs into the cells of solid wood, wood particles, virgin and recycled wood fibres by impregnation and in addition optimize the bioPCMs uptake to eliminate leaching;
- Developing and manufacturing three bio-binders for wood-based composites with bioPCM using a) polymerizable plant oils, b) lignin, and c) fungal mycelia;
- Demonstrating the above technologies by production of wood composites with bioPCM as building material (wallboards) and wood flooring (parquet) with improved thermal performance;
- Demonstrating wood construction prototype buildings with integrated novel wallboards and parquet and evaluate the energy-saving performance in Sweden and Spain;
- Employing *ex-ante* life cycle assessment (LCA) for each product and investigate long-term recyclability to ensure that the materials meet improved sustainability, circularity, and safety standards;
- Engaging in clustering activities with other European projects and initiatives of relevance;
- Determining the industrial, environmental, social and economic challenges and benefits of the new technologies to facilitate their market uptake and transferability to other bio-based materials.

T1.2 Technical and market codes. The Task intends to review the available codes of the EU countries to support the activities related to standardization and business development in the area of the BIOBUILD project. The D1.2 will include a summary of existing national and/or local regulatory framework that could support the market development helping the basic requirements of the project's concept.

T1.3 Certifications strategies and requirements. Following the national, European, and local certification standards identified in Task 1.2, the most important of them will be summarized to identify the possible barriers encountered in the market deployment. An operative analysis will conduct to identified the main existing standards and obtain the main requirements for required certifications (i.e., from existing European standards) in the design and production process of buildings.

D1.1 sets building typologies, while D1.2 sets technical and market codes and key performance indicators to address the performance assessment in WP1. Data from EU Directives for buildings, as well as from harmonised European standards (i.e., Directive (EU) 2018/844, EUROCODES standards) will be used to identify the building requirements for technical and market codes and for certification, for residential buildings in the 5 climate zones of Europe takes in consideration in D1.1.

The main results of this deliverable are:

- Building typologies considering the climatic zones in Europe for the needs of the project;
- Existing standards in the area of bio-composites used in building materials and related fields (focusing on flooring, walls and ceilings);
- Existing European standards in the area of technical codes, market codes and certification of products in EU, in the area of building materials and related fields;
- Potential gaps in existing standards, based on the correlation of the end-user's needs and existing standards;

- Possible recommendations for future standardisation works, based on the identified gaps and existing opportunities.

In many of the EU countries, the central authorities are involved in setting technical building regulations, however the involvement of regional and local authorities varies.

Technical building regulations can be set in one main document, a coordinated group of documents or separated legal documents. The formulation, adopted for most subjects, is performance-based and combined with functional or prescriptive requirements for specific subjects.

The building regulations include the main subjects (i.e., safety, health, practicability and energy saving), but several countries have none or are limited regarding specific requirements on environmental protection. In the majority of the EU countries, direct references to specific standards are made, but standards are not easy accessible for SMEs.

On the other hand, the literature specifies that there is not a pattern in the way that building regulations apply to construction works in existing buildings.

The document is divided in five chapters. A brief overview of the deliverable structure is provided hereafter.

- Chapter 1 is an introductory section of the document and a general overview of the deliverable.
- Chapter 2 is the methodological approach.
- Chapter 3 addresses the technical and market codes for products for residential and office buildings.
- Chapter 4 addresses the certifications strategies and requirements in the area of building sustainability, and in the environmental foot and quality of construction products.
- Chapter 5 summarises the basic conclusions of the analysis and recommendations for the other WPs.

2 Approach and methodology

The authors of the report intended to identify and collect a helpful enough documentation (European and national standards, requirements for certification of building products) for the other WPs of the project (especially WP2 and WP6), that should be able to rely on D1.2. Three major topics were analysed.

1. Identification and a brief analysis of existing standards in the area of the project (EUROCODES standards, international/European standards used for market codes, product certification etc., especially for bio-materials and methodologies for flooring, walls and ceilings). For the bio-based industry the European Commission identified that standards are needed to promote the uptake of its products by consumers, facilitate the functioning of the Single Market, and enable public authorities to implement 'green procurement' policies.
Mandated by the European Commission, the CEN/TC 411 'Bio-based products' developed standards that cover the horizontal aspects of bio-based products. These standards play a crucial role in supporting the growth of the bio-based product market. They can help to increase the market transparency by providing common reference methods and requirements that enable the verification of claims and certification regarding the bio-based content, bio-degradability or environmental sustainability of various products.
2. Technical and market codes for wood products in Europe. These codes help in identifying and categorizing various types of wood products for technical and market purposes. Each EU country typically has its system of technical standards and market codes for wood products, which may vary slightly. However, some overarching EU-wide standards and regulations apply to wood products traded within the European Union.
3. European and international (that apply in EU) certification schemes, especially applied to wood products. Certification is a procedure by which a third party gives written assurance that a product, process or service is in conformity with certain standards. Over the recent years many certificates have been developed by NGOs, authorities or certification bodies to help consumers, manufacturers, distributors and traders choose the right products for their purpose and provide conformance testing. Among others, certificates help to demonstrate the sustainability of biomass, the bio-based content of a product or the end-of-life options. As a result, many certification schemes are available in the market. Implementing standards and achieving standards accreditation comes at certain costs. These costs tend to be fixed irrespective of scale, and thus adversely affect starters or small producers.

3 Technical and market codes of products for residential and office buildings

3.1 Introduction

A building code (also building control or building regulations) is a set of rules that specify the standards for construction objects such as buildings and non-building structures. Buildings must conform to the code to obtain planning permission, usually from a local council. The main purpose of the building codes is to protect public health, safety and general welfare as they relate to the construction and occupancy of buildings and structures – for example, the building codes in many countries require the engineers to consider the effects of soil liquefaction in the design of new buildings. A building code becomes law of a particular jurisdiction when formally enacted by the appropriate governmental or private authority.

The building codes have a long history. The earliest known written building code is included in the Code of Hammurabi, which dates from ca. 1772 BC [1]. The book of Deuteronomy in the Hebrew Bible stipulated that parapets must be constructed on all houses to prevent people from falling off [2]. During the modern era, under the reconstruction of Paris during the Second Empire (1852-1870), great blocks of apartments were erected, and the height of buildings was limited by law to five or six floors at most.

The first systematic national building standard was established by the London Building Act of 1844. Among the provisions, builders were required to give the district surveyor two days' notice before building, regulations regarding the thickness of walls, height of rooms, the materials used in repairs, the plan of existing buildings, the placing and design of chimneys, fireplaces and drains were to be enforced and the streets had to be built to minimum requirements [3].

Now, in every European country, there is a building regulatory system encompassing the building regulations and the building control system. Building regulations set minimum quality requirements to ensure that buildings are safe, healthy, energy-efficient and accessible to everyone who lives and works in and around them. Building control aims to guarantee the application and enforcement of these minimum requirements. The purpose and the subjects covered by the building regulations are identical in European Union (EU) countries. However, there are many differences between countries regarding who sets the building regulations, how the technical building regulations are organized and formulated, what is the role of national standards and how building regulations apply to existing buildings.

European building policy has been under development since the 1990s. Under the leadership of the European Commission, building standards and policies have gradually improved, considering issues such as financing solutions, renewable energies, indoor environmental quality, and the alleviation of energy poverty.

Codes for wood products in Europe typically follow the standards set by organizations like the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) or the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). These codes help in identifying and categorizing various types of wood products for technical and market purposes.

Some authors [4] classified five main types of organization and formulation of technical building regulations in the EU countries, as shown below.

1. One document with functional requirements and a coordinated group of documents with deemed to satisfy solutions.
2. One document with performance requirements.
3. One document with prescriptive requirements and new performance regulations on specific subjects.
4. A set of coordinated documents with performance requirements.
5. Separated legal documents mainly with performance requirements combined with some prescriptive requirements.

Although there are exceptions, a regional distribution was observed in the countries that adopt each type.

In more than a half of the EU countries there are no specific technical building regulations for existing buildings [4]. When there are building regulations for existing buildings, they usually apply to a particular scope (e.g., reconversion of illegal urban areas) or concern specific requirements (e.g., up-grade of technical equipment). Construction works in existing buildings are treated differently by the general technical building regulations of the EU countries. The following two main approaches were identified.

1. General building regulations apply to all construction works, but for existing buildings relaxations of the provisions are possible (e.g., Austria, Cyprus, France, Latvia and The Netherlands).
2. General building regulations apply to new buildings (e.g., Ireland, Portugal, Slovenia, England and Wales), and to reconstruction, extension, extensive renovation or change in use of existing buildings. Small renovations and maintenance works are usually excluded from complying with building regulations for new buildings.

The building regulations for existing buildings can be used passively or actively. Passively, if the building must comply with the regulations when construction works are carried out. Actively, if the authorities can summon the owner to carry out quality improvement of buildings that do not comply with the building regulations. In Europe, around 40% of the existing building stock was constructed before the 1960s when building energy codes were minimal. Nowadays energy codes for buildings comprise the energy efficiency requirements for newly constructed or renovated buildings. These requirements may apply to the building envelope and/or systems and can cover end uses such as heating, ventilation, air conditioning, lighting and water heating.

The purpose of building regulations is to provide minimum standards for safety, health, and general welfare including structural integrity, mechanical integrity (including sanitation, water supply, light, and ventilation), means of egress, fire prevention and control, and energy conservation [6]. The building codes generally include:

- Standards for structure, placement, size, usage, wall assemblies, fenestration size/locations, egress rules, size/location of rooms, foundations, floor assemblies, roof structures/assemblies, energy efficiency, stairs and halls, mechanical, electrical, plumbing, site drainage and storage, appliance, lighting, fixtures standards, occupancy rules, and swimming pool regulations, like EUROCODES.
- Rules regarding parking and traffic impact.
- Fire code rules to minimize the risk of a fire and to ensure safe evacuation in the event of an emergency.
- Requirements for earthquake (seismic code), hurricane, flood, and tsunami resistance, especially in disaster prone areas or for very large buildings where a failure would be catastrophic.
- Requirements for specific building uses (for example, storage of flammable substances, or housing many people, like stadiums or halls for sports events).
- Energy provisions and consumption.
- Specifications on components.
- Allowable installation methodologies.
- Minimum and maximum room ceiling heights, exit sizes and location.
- Qualification of individuals or corporations doing the work.
- For high structures, anti-collision markers for the benefit of aircraft.

3.2 Types of combined nomenclature (market codes) needed for wood products in buildings

Coding and marking requirements in the wood subsector vary considerably depending on the type of product being produced. This huge and varied area includes everything from raw timber used in construction to coated and varnished products for furniture, flooring, and other finished items. Specific coding requirements may include the following:

- Dimensions and specification.
- Structural ratings.
- Stress grade test results.
- Timber species identification.
- Date, time, shift, and batch codes.
- Product codes.

- Company branding and logo.
- Barcodes and 2D data codes.
- Association trademarks such as Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) or Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC).

Wood and wooden articles are classified in the European Classification of Goods [5] CN², according to how much they have been worked, their nature and purpose and the type of wood they are made from. Some articles – though not all – must meet specific size requirements to be classified under certain heading codes. Specialist terms are often used to describe both woodworking processes and articles made of wood. Timber and wooden items may be classified according to whether they are – or are made from – i.e., wood from coniferous, deciduous or tropical wood species.

Wood sheets of veneer for making plywood or similar laminated products are classified under heading code 4408. To be classified under this heading code, these sheets must not be thicker than 6 mm. The sheets can be spliced, taped, stitched or glued together edge to edge to make larger sheets for use in plywood and similar laminated wood. Sheets may also be planed, sanded, end-jointed or finger-jointed, possibly in a zig-zag pattern. Sheets for veneering may also be produced by slicing blocks of laminated wood – as a substitute for veneer sheets made by the traditional method. The classification of sheets for plywood is not affected if a defect has been patched with paper, plastic or wood.

Moulded wood built up by superimposing a mould onto another piece of moulded or unmoulded wood is not classified under heading code 4409. Instead, it is classified under heading codes 4418 or 4421. The following products are also not classified under the heading code 4409:

- Plywood or veneered strips and friezes. These are classified under heading code 4412.
- Strips of plywood or veneered wood for parquet flooring. These are classified under heading code 4412.
- Planed or other worked boards presented in sets as box boards. These are classified under heading code 4415.
- Wood that has been mortised, tenoned, dovetailed or similarly worked at the ends. Wood assembled into panels, such as carpentry, joinery and parquet flooring panels. These are all classified under heading code 4418.
- Panels that are made up of laths of roughly sawn wood, assembled with glue for transportation or for working on later. These are classified under heading code 4421.
- Wood that has been bronzed or had metal leaf added. This is generally classified under heading code 4421.

Particle boards, oriented strand boards (OSB) and similar boards such as wafer-boards are classified under heading code 4410. Particle boards, commonly known as chipboards, are flat products that are manufactured in various sizes by pressing or extrusion. It is classified under subheading code 4410 11 and is generally made from:

- wood chips or particles resulting from the reduction of round wood;
- wood residues;
- fragments of wood or other ligneous materials such as bagasse, bamboo, cereal straw and flax.

These materials are agglomerated by a resin or other organic binder to form the particle board. The particle boards are usually sanded and may be impregnated with one or more substances to provide waterproofing, resistance to microorganism and insect attack, fire or the spread of flame, chemicals, etc. Extruded particle boards may have holes running internally from end to end.

OSB evolved from wafer-board. OSB is different from wafer-boards in that the wood strands are oriented and not randomly placed. Both OSB and wafer-boards are engineered from strands, flakes or wafers sliced from

² The EU classification system has 2 elements.

- The Combined Nomenclature (CN) - the EU's 8-digit coding system. It is based on the Harmonized Commodity Description and Coding System (HS) - developed by the World Customs Organisation (WCO).
- The CN is used for the EU's common customs tariff. It is also used to provide EU trade statistics.

The Integrated Tariff (TARIC) provides information on all trade policy and tariff measures that apply to specific goods in the EU (e.g. temporary suspension of duties, antidumping duties). It is made up of the 8-digit code of the CN plus 2 extra digits (TARIC subheadings).

small diameter, round wood logs and bonded with an exterior-type binder under heat and pressure. OSB is classified under subheading code 4410 12.

Wafer-board is a structural panel board made from large, thin wafers of wood or other ligneous material. The wafers look like pieces of veneer and are coated with waterproof glue and bonded together under heat and pressure. Wafer-board is classified under subheading code 4410 90. The heading code 4410 also includes:

- particle board and similar wood board that is covered with plastics, paint, paper, textile materials or metal;
- particle board and laminated panels made of several particle boards covered on one or both faces with fibreboards;
- laminated panels consisting of several particle boards and several fibreboards assembled in any order.

Cellular wood panels that have particle board on both faces are not classified under heading code 4410. Instead, they are classified under heading code 4418.

Fibreboard is made from wood and other ligneous material fibres and may or may not be bonded with a resin or other organic substance. Fibreboard can be shaped – for example curved, corrugated or perforated – and cut or formed to shapes other than square or rectangular. It may also be surfaced, edge worked, coated or covered with textile, plastics, paint, paper or metal. For classification purposes, sanding is not considered to be a mechanical working. Fibreboard is classified under heading code 4411 and may be high, medium or low density.

Fibreboard obtained by the "dry production process" includes in particular medium density fibreboard (MDF) which is manufactured in a process in which additional thermosetting resins are added to the dried wood fibres in order to assist the bonding process in the press. The density ranges from 0.45 g/cm³ to 1g/cm³. In the unworked state it has two smooth surfaces. Medium density fibreboard of a density exceeding 0.8 g/cm³ is sometimes also referred to by the trade as "high density fibreboard (HDF)".

Plywood, veneered panels and similar laminated wood products are classified under heading code 4412. These products may be worked to form shapes – for example curved, corrugated or perforated – and cut or formed to shapes other than square or rectangular. Plywood that is made from coniferous species often has defects – or hollows – on the outer ply that have been repaired with wood inlays or plastic filler compounds during the manufacturing process. These materials are not considered to be additional substances and do not affect the classification of plywood under the heading code 4412.

Plywood may be unsanded or further prepared by sanding. The term 'unsanded' includes 'touch-sanded', which is the process of smoothing irregularities on the outer ply caused by patching, plugging or filling.

The types of products that are classified under heading code 4412 include:

- blockboards;
- laminboards;
- battenboards.

They also include:

- plywood or veneered panels, used as flooring panels and sometimes referred to as 'parquet flooring' – these panels have a thin veneer of wood fixed to the surface to make them look like flooring panels made up of parquet strips;
- laminated wooden panels for doors – known as 'door blanks' – that have a block-board type core. The exposed edges of the core may be made up of pieces of wood known as 'lippings' and the edges may also be veneered. These panels may have been further worked, for example by adding hinges or other door furniture.

Densified wood is classified under heading code 4413. It may be in the form of blocks, plates, strips and profile shapes and the most commonly densified wood species are beech, hornbeam, acacia (robinia, black locust)³ and poplar. The densification can be done at the same time as impregnation by gluing very thin sheets of wood - usually beech - with thermosetting plastics under heavy pressure at a high temperature to deeply impregnate, compress and bond the wood.

Builders' joinery and carpentry articles are classified under heading code 4418. They include cellular wood panels, assembled flooring panels, shingles and shakes.

Joinery means builders' fittings like doors, windows, stairs and door and window frames. Carpentry means woodwork such as beams, rafters and roof struts that are used for structural purposes or for scaffolding, arch supports and so on. It also includes assembled shuttering for concrete building work and glue laminated timber, so-called 'glulam'.

Solid laminated wood panels with thick cores are classified under subheading code 4418 20. In case they have been further worked, they are clearly only for use as doors and their frames and thresholds. For example, they could have recesses for handles, locks and hinges cut into them. Unworked panels – sometimes known as solid core door blanks – are not classified under this subheading code, even if their edges are veneered. Instead they are classified under the heading code 4412.

Assembled flooring panels are classified under subheading code 4418 73 or 4418 79. These panels consist of a 'wear layer', made of blocks, strips and friezes that are assembled on a backing of an appropriate material, like wood, particle board, paper, plastic and cork. Panels for mosaic floors are prefabricated panels made of several separate square or rectangular elements. They may include cabochons, which are uncut, highly polished gemstones. The strips are laid out according to a certain pattern, such as chequered, basket-weave and herringbone.

Wood flooring

There is no single commodity code that covers all types of wood flooring. Instead, classification depends on what the floor is made of, in some cases how it is made and the type of wood used – solid wood, wood fibres, tropical, plastic or laminated wood.

Sheets of sliced or peeled (rotary cut) wood, strips and friezes for parquet flooring are classified under heading code 4407. These wood products are not fully prepared and does not give the finished appearance of parquet flooring. It has not been worked beyond planning, sanding or end-jointing.

Wood that is continuously shaped, for example tongued or grooved, along any of its edges or faces is classified under heading code 4409.

Flooring with a MDF-board core which is tongued and grooved ('lock system') and a surface of a photographic wood image on paper simulating a parquet panel which has an overlay of melamine resin (varnish) for protection and has a base made of impregnated paper is classified under 4411.

Strips of plywood or veneered wood for parquet flooring – which may or may not be continuously shaped along any of their edges or faces – are classified under heading code 4412. This heading code also includes plywood panels or veneered panels that are used as flooring panels and that have a thin veneer of wood fixed to the surface to make them look like flooring panels made up of parquet strips. These may or may not be continuously shaped along any of their edges or faces.

Parquet strips that are assembled into panels or tiles are classified under heading code 4418.

Non-assembled strips and friezes for parquet flooring – consisting of narrow pieces of board which have been continuously shaped along any of their edges or faces – are classified under heading code 4409.

³ Robinia and Acacia are species of trees which look similar. Acacia is tropical timber, native to Africa, Australia and South America. Robinia on the other hand is an Eastern European timber. Robinia is also known as False Acacia because of its similar appearance.

The black locust is commonly referred to as "false acacia" after its species name "pseudoacacia", although it is not particularly closely related to the acacia, which belongs to the mimosa subfamily (Mimosoideae).

Cellular wood panels and assembled parquet panels or tiles – including those consisting of parquet strips assembled on a support of one or more layers of wood – are classified under heading code 4418.

Some of the wood flooring terms used under the Tariff code (TARIC) - are listed and explained below:

- basket pattern - assembly of fingers, blocks or strips placed edge to edge, to make up a square, the side of which is the same length as the finger, block or strip.
- brick pattern - parquet made up of pieces of equal length and width, where the end joint is at the centre of the juxtaposed element.
- engineered wood - layers of hardwood compressed together, like solid wood. It can be sanded and renovated after laying.
- French flooring - flooring made up of pieces that have a random length and a series of widths, arranged in a parallel direction.
- herringbone - parquet made up of pieces of the same size, with the ends cut at a right angle, laid perpendicular to one another, at an angle of 45 degrees in relation to the direction of the walls or battens.
- Hungarian pattern - parquet made up of pieces of the same size, with the ends cut at an angle of 45 and 60 degrees, that are laid end to end at a right angle or at an angle of 120 degrees, forming parallel patterns.
- laminated - laminated wood shouldn't be confused with laminated plastic or paper. Some modern laminated flooring uses a photographic representation of wood on plastic or paper that's applied to high density fibreboard or a similar product. This type of laminate doesn't age and usually can't be sanded and renovated like solid wood.
- multi-layer flooring - wood flooring with a top layer thickness of at least 2.5 millimetres before installation.
- parquet - wood flooring with a top layer thickness of at least 2.5 millimetres before installation.
- parquet panel - pre-assembled laying unit made up from parquet pieces.
- planking - this is available in various widths, either with tongue and groove in lengths or as plain square-edged planks that simply butt up against one another.
- solid wood block parquet - uniform brick-like blocks - usually oak - laid in a herringbone, brick, ladder or basket formation.
- solid wood parquet - made up of different coloured hardwood sections to create decorative patterning. This type of floor is usually allowed to acclimatise to the building where it's to be laid, as the timber's moisture content can vary. This causes expansion and contraction so the wood needs time to stabilise.
- strip pattern - parquet made up of an assembly of equal width but random length strips.
- veneer - a single thin or fine layer of wood that has been glued to a manufactured base. Veneer floors are generally fitted 'floating' - which means they're not fixed to a sub-floor. They lie on a foam or cork underlay and must have a flat, even surface beneath them.
- wood block - floors made up from small strips or blocks of wood, around three inches wide and nine inches long, arranged in herringbone, basket-weave and other geometric patterns.
- wood laminate - has thin layers of wood that are glued to a manufactured base.
- wood planks - come in long lengths with widths of 10 centimetres or more.
- wood strip - boards are narrower and shorter than planks and have up to three strips of wood per board.

The European Standards for specific wood flooring products and parquets which provide product definitions and requirements for dimensional tolerances, include the following:

- solid parquet elements with tongues and grooves (EN 13226);
- solid lamparquet products (EN 13227);
- solid wood overlay elements including blocks with an interlocking system (EN 13228);
- mosaic parquet elements (EN 13488);
- multi-layer parquet elements (EN 13489);
- solid pre-assembled hardwood board (EN 13629);
- solid softwood floor boards (EN 13990);
- wood veneer floor coverings (EN 14354);
- solid wood parquet – vertical finger, wide finger and module brick (EN 14761).

3.3 EUROCODES

The EN Eurocodes are a series of 10 European Standards, EN 1990 – EN 1999, providing a common approach for the design of buildings and other civil engineering works and construction products. They are the recommended reference for technical specifications in public contracts.

The Eurocodes development started, because of the decision of the Commission of the European Community to embark on an action programme in the field of construction based on Article 95 of the Treaty of Rome. The objective of the programme was the elimination of technical obstacles to trade and the harmonisation of technical specifications by means of technical rules which, in the first stage, would serve as an alternative to the national rules in force in the Member States and, ultimately, would replace them.

In 1980 an International Inquiry regarding construction codes of practice was performed and in 1984 the first Eurocodes were published by the Commission with the help of a Steering Committee containing representatives of Member States. A great help was the development of the Construction Products Directive which defines the essential requirements that construction products must fulfil.

In 1990 European standards development started, following a Mandate issued in 1989 by the Commission and the Member States, based on an agreement with CEN, endorsed by the Standing Committee on Construction. The preparation and publication of the Eurocodes was transferred to CEN. The Eurocodes were intended to become European Standards.

Publication of Eurocodes standards by CEN begun in 1992. Due to difficulties in harmonizing all the aspects of the calculation methods, the Eurocodes standards included "boxed values" which allowed Member States to choose values for use on their territory. National Application Documents, which gave the details of how to apply the Eurocodes standards in Member States, were issued together with a country's national annex prepared by an NSB.

The Commission Recommendation on the implementation and use of Eurocodes was issued in 2003. The EN Eurocodes are the recommended set of standards for the design of products and structures that satisfy the essential requirements of mechanical resistance and stability, as well as safety in case of fire. Member States are encouraged to adopt the recommended values of NDPs (Nationally Determined Parameters) and to contribute to the promotion, further harmonization and development of the EN Eurocodes.

The EN Eurocodes are the result of a long procedure of bringing together and harmonising the different design traditions in the Member States. In the same time, the Member States keep exclusive competence and responsibility for the levels of safety of works. The differences in the environmental conditions and in the ways of life in the Member States also require flexibility in the National Application of the EN Eurocodes. Therefore, the EN Eurocodes include NDPs which:

- take into account differences in geographical, geological or climatic conditions;
- result from different design cultures and procedures for structural analysis;
- arise from the requirement for safety levels in the relevant Member States.

In all 59 parts of the Eurocodes there are 1 573 Nationally Determined Parameters (NDPs). In a number of cases, an NDP cannot be represented by a single numerical value. In fact, many NDPs take the form of tables, graphs, acceptance of the recommended procedure, choice of calculation approach among given alternatives, introduction of a new procedure, etc.

EN 1991: Actions on structures contains a big number of NDPs (Figure 1), most of them arising from different geographical, geological and climatic conditions. Further harmonisation will be sought regarding the methodologies used for the assessment of these NDPs.

The database of NDPs is managed by the Safety and Security of Buildings Unit of the DG Joint Research Centre of the European Commission.

Figure 1. Number and percentage of NDPs per EN Eurocode [7]

By 17 January 2022, the acceptance average of the recommended values (RVs) was 73%, Figure 2 [7]. The analysis was based on 72% of the NDPs with RVs that are expected to be uploaded in the Database.

Figure 2. Acceptance of recommended values per country by 2022 [7]

In 2012, DG GROW of the European Commission issued the Mandate M/515 for a detailed work programme for amending existing Eurocodes and extending the scope of structural Eurocodes. The work of CEN/Technical Committee (TC) 250 “Structural Eurocodes” (CEN/TC 250) under the Mandate M/515 started in 2016. CEN/TC 250 successfully completed the largest Standardisation Request under M/515 at the end of 2022.

The definitive text of second generation EN Eurocode parts in the official language versions will be distributed by the Central Secretariat to National Standards Bodies (NSBs) as soon as possible after Formal Vote and no later than 30 March 2026 (Date of availability – DAV), Figure 3.

All second generation EN Eurocodes will have a Date of publication (DoP) of 30 September 2027. DoP is the latest date by which an EN standard has to be implemented at national level (by publication of an identical national standard or by endorsement), Figure 4.

All second generation EN Eurocodes will have a Date of withdrawal (DoW) of 30 March 2028. DoW is the latest date by which national standards conflicting with the EN (i.e. in this case first generation Eurocode parts) must be withdrawn.

Figure 3. Eurocode development process [8]

Figure 4. Overview of CEN/TC 250 approach for DoP and DoW [8]

At first glance, the Eurocodes standards do not have a direct involvement in the BIOBUILD project, but upon closer examination we found the following:

- With regard to floor structures, the Eurocodes give only recommendations for estimated limits for Eigenfrequencies, i.e., 3 Hz or 8 Hz depending on the construction material (for design of floor structures for human-induced vibrations), or they give a reference to ISO-standards as ISO 10137:2007 (Bases for design of structures – Serviceability of buildings and walkways against vibrations, confirmed 2024) and ISO 2631-1:1997 (Mechanical vibration and shock – Evaluation of human exposure to whole-body vibration. Part 1: General requirements, confirmed in 2021), which give general criteria for the perception of vibrations and could be the basis to develop more detailed design rules for vibrations specific to structures and types of excitations.
- Where floors are likely to be subject to dancing and jumping activities characterised by synchronised crowd movement, the floor must be designed for ultimate limit state consideration in accordance with the requirements given in EN 1991.1.1 (sometimes supplement by NA):
 - the floor may be designed to have a fundamental frequency of at least 8.4 Hz vertically and at least 4 Hz horizontally, in which case the resonant effect need to be evaluated.
 - the floor should be designed to resist anticipate dynamic loads due to rhythmic activity, which should be considered as an additional imposed load case.

- EN 1994-1-1 (Eurocode 4) presented general design and application rules for shallow floor beams, with a particular focus on a) the classification of the composite cross-section; b) non-linear bending resistance; and c) the introduction of transverse bars as shear connectors.
- Eurocode 5: Design of timber structures – Part 1-1: General common rules and rules for buildings, apply to the design of buildings and civil engineering works in timber (solid timber, sawn, planed or in pole form, glued laminated timber or wood-based structural products, e.g., LVL) or wood-based panels jointed together with adhesives or mechanical fasteners. It complies with the principles and requirements for the safety and serviceability of structures and the basis of design and verification given in EN 1990.
 - Wood-based panels shall comply with EN 13986 and LVL (Laminated veneer lumber, defined according to EN 14279 and EN 14374) used as panels shall comply with EN 14279.
 - The use of softboards according to EN 622-4 should be restricted to wind bracing and should be designed by testing.
 - Adhesives for structural purposes shall produce joints of such strength and durability that the integrity of the bond is maintained in the assigned service class throughout the expected life of the structure.
 - Adhesives which comply with Type I specification as defined in EN 301 may be used in all service classes. Adhesives which comply with Type II specification as defined in EN 301 should only be used in accordance with Annex 1 from EN 301.
 - Timber and wood-based materials shall either have adequate natural durability in accordance with EN 350-2 for the particular hazard class (defined in EN 335-1, EN 335-2 and EN 335-3), or be given a preservative treatment selected in accordance with EN 351-1 and EN 460.
- NOTE 1: Preservative treatment may affect the strength and stiffness properties of wood.
- NOTE 2: Rules for specification of preservation treatments are given in EN 350-2 and EN 335.

3.4 Energy codes for buildings

Enforcing energy-related requirements during the design or retrofit phase of a building is a key driver for implementing energy efficiency measures in the building sector. Strong building energy codes cannot only bring substantial CO₂ savings and reduced energy bills, but also ensure more comfortable occupant conditions, more employment opportunities and increased energy security. Understanding the latest developments in building codes requires continuous monitoring and evaluation of what is adopted and enforced at country, regional and local level.

Energy codes for buildings comprise the energy efficiency requirements for newly constructed or renovated buildings. These requirements may apply to the building envelope and/or systems and can cover end uses such as heating, ventilation, air conditioning, lighting and water heating.

In Europe, energy codes for buildings are in a dynamic phase. The energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD, 2002/91/EC) was a major step forward through which Member States (MS) introduced requirements based on a “whole building” approach. In addition to overall building performance, a shift from an approach typically covering maximum permitted U-value⁴ only to a more extensive one including technical system requirements (e.g., on HVAC and lighting) has occurred. Moreover, major revisions in the building energy codes should be applied through the consideration of the cost optimality concept followed by the adoption of nearly zero energy standards.

Eighty-five percent (85%) of EU buildings were built before 2000 and amongst those, 75% have a poor energy performance. Acting on the energy efficiency of buildings is therefore the key of saving energy, reducing bills for citizens and small enterprises and achieving a zero-emission and fully decarbonised building stock by 2050. These facts, and those below, come from Eurostat energy balances and EEA Greenhouse Gas Inventory, 2023 [9]:

- around 40% of energy consumed in the EU is used in buildings;
- over 1/3 of the EU's energy-related GHG emissions come from buildings;
- ± 80% of energy used in EU homes is for heating, cooling and hot water.

⁴ U-value, or thermal transmittance (reciprocal of R-value)

Thermal transmittance, also known as U-value, is the rate of transfer of heat through a structure (which can be a single material or a composite), divided by the difference in temperature across that structure. The units of measurement are W/m²K. The better-insulated a structure is, the lower the U-value will be.

To boost the energy performance of buildings, the EU has established a legislative framework that includes the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EU/2024/1275) and the revised Energy Efficiency Directive (EU/2023/1791). The directives promote policies that will help to:

- achieve a highly energy efficient and decarbonised building stock by 2050;
- create a stable environment for investment decisions;
- enable consumers and businesses to make more informed choices to save energy and money.

Figure 5 European Climate and Energy Legislation and Initiatives [10]

The EU has set the goal of improving energy efficiency by 32.5% by 2030 and reaching a decarbonised building stock by 2050. This can only be done by setting milestones underpinned by targeted measures, and providing dedicated funding streams that help to achieve the specific policy targets. The National Energy and Climate Plans (NECP), which are closely interlinked with national long-term renovation strategies (LTRS), must provide this information and outline how Member States plan to reach their climate and energy targets.

The European legislation covers and connects a range of topics to support high performance and decarbonisation of the building stock. These include the calculation of the energy performance of buildings, energy performance certificates, metering of energy consumption and building automation, but also the split-incentive dilemma and the alleviation of energy poverty, which have a clear social impact.

In addition to legislation, the EU has also adopted a series of initiatives to support Member States, increase knowledge about EU building stock, and monitor its progress over time: the Building Stock observatory (BSO) collects data on all building typologies across the EU; while the national databases on energy performance certificates are meant to provide up-to-date information on the performance of buildings sold, rented or which have undergone major renovations. LTRS and NECP also provide data on national building stock. This can help to assess the achievement of goals, compare the countries and building types, and monitor the effectiveness of policies and financial instruments.

The EPBD serves as the primary legislation guiding building construction and renovation in the EU to enhance building performance and efficiency to achieve the 2030 and 2050 energy targets. The directive was adopted in 2002, recast in 2010, amended in 2018. The last revision on EPBD directive was in May 2024. The latest amendments to the directive set a clear direction for the full decarbonisation of EU building stock by 2050, with an increased emphasis on building renovation and modernisation. This goal, accompanied by a roadmap and suggested measures to achieve that vision with national long-term renovation strategies, should be the driver for increased renovation activities in the EU.

Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) - Introduced in 2002, Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are now commonly used across Europe aiming at informing building owners, occupiers and property actors on a) energy performance of buildings to ensure that they can be compared and assessed to make informed decisions; and b) practical ways to improve the energy efficiency of buildings and their performance class (e.g., A or G).

According to the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), Member States must establish the necessary measures to create a system of certification of the energy performance of buildings. They must be issued by independent energy experts.

An EPC must include the energy performance of a building and reference values such as minimum energy performance requirements to make it possible for owners or tenants of the building or building unit to compare and assess energy performance. They also include information on how to improve the performance of the building. EPCs may include additional information such as the annual energy consumption and the percentage of energy from renewable sources in the total energy consumption.

Obligation to issue and display EPC when rented or sold.

The Member States shall ensure that an EPC is issued for:

- Buildings or building units which are constructed, sold or rented out to a new tenant; and
- Buildings where a total useful floor area over 250 m² is occupied by a public authority and frequently visited by the public. The directive also established the obligation to display the energy performance indicator of the EPC in advertisements.

The EPBD 2024 starts on 1st of January 2028 for publicly owned buildings and 1st of January 2030 for all other buildings. The EPBD considers the following:

Minimum Energy Performance Standards for existing buildings

For residential buildings: a national trajectory must be adopted by the Member States to reduce the energy use at least by 16% by 2030 and 20-22% by 2035 (they are free to decide on the appropriate measures and the targeted buildings). However, prioritizing the worst-performing buildings is mandatory.

Strengthened Certification Schemes

To ensure clarity, reliability and visibility, Energy Performance Certificates ("EPC") will adopt a standardized template across all Member States. The new EPC system will establish an A-G scale, "A" being reserved for zero-emission buildings, while "G" will be assigned to the least energy-efficient buildings. Member States will also have the option to introduce an "A+" class for those building that exceed zero-emission standards and produce more renewable energy than they consume.

Renovation Prioritization and Funding Mechanisms

Building Renovation Passport: these documents will offer personalized renovation roadmaps tailored to the specific characteristics and needs of each building, will include a comprehensive assessment of the building's current energy performance and potential areas for improvement, will provide technical recommendations for energy-saving measures and renovation options and should be prepared and issued concurrently with the energy performance certificate by the same qualified expert. It will be up to Member States to create the national framework for the renovation passports, which shall be of voluntary use, unless Member State decide to make it mandatory.

National Building Renovation Plans

EU Member States will develop comprehensive strategies to provide a policy framework for guiding energy-efficient efforts across various sectors of the economy. These strategies will include specific targets and objectives for energy efficiency improvements in buildings and assessments of the existing building stock. A standardized template featuring both compulsory and optional components is implemented to enhance consistency among Member States. Initial plans are to be presented to the Commission by December 2025.

Indisputably, the EPBD will pose a significant challenge for the real estate sector, requiring considerable investment and resulting in major changes in the design, construction, and operation of buildings. Nevertheless, the benefits for all stakeholders should be commensurate, such as enhancing the future investment value and marketability of buildings or contributing to the EU's climate and energy goals (by reducing GHG emissions, increasing renewable energy use, and improving energy efficiency, in line with the Paris Agreement and the Green Deal).

Energy performance of buildings standards

The Commission has established a set of standards and accompanying technical reports to support the EPBD called the energy performance of buildings standards (EPB standards). These are managed by the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN).

The five 'overarching' EPB standards ISO 52000-1, 52003-1, 52010-1, 52016-1 and 52018-1 have in common that each of these describes an important step in the assessment of the energy performance of building.

- **ISO 52000-1** is the overarching EPB standard, providing the general framework of the EPB assessment. It establishes a systematic, comprehensive and modular structure for assessing the energy performance of new and existing buildings (EPB) in a holistic way.
It is applicable to the assessment of overall energy use of a building, by measurement or calculation, and the calculation of energy performance in terms of primary energy or other energy-related metrics. It considers the specific possibilities and limitations for the different applications, such as building design, new buildings 'as built', and existing buildings in the use phase as well as renovation. It also contains an overview of common terms and definitions and symbols for the whole set of EPB standards.
- **ISO 52003-1** provides general insight on how to make good use of the outputs of the set of EPB assessment standards for different purposes (post-processing) in the form of overall and partial EPB indicators. It describes the relation between the EPB indicators and the EPB requirements and EPB ratings. It also includes a couple of possible EPB labels, and it lists the different steps to be taken when establishing an EPB certification scheme.
- **ISO 52010-1** contains procedures to assess the climatic data needed as common input or boundary condition for many elements in the energy calculations. For instance, it serves as input for energy and daylighting calculations, for building elements (roofs, facades and windows) and for components of technical building systems (thermal solar collectors, PV panels). Additionally it serves as boundary condition for the performance of specific heating, cooling and ventilation systems.
- **ISO 52016-1** provides the procedures to calculate the internal temperatures and energy needs for heating and cooling for the building as such. This is the core of the calculation of the energy use, because many aspects coincide in this calculation: thermal insulation, air tightness and ventilation, the building mass, solar heat load and passive solar energy and internal heat gains (e.g., from lighting).
Many countries have introduced or consider introducing specific EPB requirements at the level of 'the energy needs' of the building or the 'skin' or 'fabric' of the building, independent from the choice of technical building systems and renewable energy systems.
- **ISO 52018-1** provides an overview of options of indicators enabling (optional) specific EPB requirements (post-processing) at the level of the building as such (building energy needs or building fabric).

Indeed, there are many other standards that should be named as EPB standards. An "EPB standard" is a standard that complies with the requirements given in the following three documents: CEN/TS 16628, the basic principles for EPB standards, CEN/TS 16629, the detailed technical rules of EPB standards and EN ISO 52000-1, the overarching EPB standard.

The first mandate to CEN to develop a set of CEN EPBD standards (M/343), to support the first edition of the EPBD resulted in the successful publication of all EPBD related CEN standards in 2007-2008. However, although these standards were implemented in many countries, in a practical way, they were not yet fit to be applied as a ready-to-use, compatible and unambiguous set.

The mandate M/480 was issued to review the initial mandate M/343 as the recast of the EPBD raised the need to revisit the standards and reformulate and add standards so that they become on the one hand unambiguous and compatible, and on the other hand a clear and explicit overview of the choices, boundary conditions and input data that need to be defined at national or regional level. Such national or regional choices remain necessary, due to differences in climate, culture & building tradition, policy and legal frameworks.

The EPB standards are flexible enough to allow for necessary national and regional differentiation and facilitate Member States implementation and the setting of requirements by the Member States. Several EPB standards have been prepared or revised as combined EN ISO standards under the so-called Vienna Agreement between CEN and ISO.

Some other CEN and ISO working groups have decided, for practical reasons, for the time being to work in parallel on separate CEN and ISO EPB standards, aiming to keep these as similar as possible, with the aim to merge these to EN ISO standards when the drafting has reached a more mature stage.

Up until now, 17 of the EPB standards are EN ISO standards: the overarching EPB standard, plus the EPB standards on building and building components (ISO/TC 163 in cooperation with CEN/TC 89). The other 30 EPB standards are up until now only available at European (CEN) level.

The intention of the work is to deliver a complete and consistent set of ISO (EN ISO) standards on the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB). A unique Joint Working Group of ISO/TC 163 and ISO/TC 205, ISO/TC 163/WG 4 co-ordinates the development of the set of EPB standards at the global (ISO) level, under the responsibility of the two ISO parent TC's.

4 Certifications strategies and requirements

4.1 Introduction in certification

Official certifications go back almost 500 years. In 1518 Thomas Linacre petitioned Henry VIII for permission to establish a college of physicians for the purpose of granting licenses to practice, and to punish “unqualified” practitioners. Over time this became the Royal College of Physicians in London. Prospective doctors had to pass exams to prove they were classically educated and possessed the sufficient medical knowledge. Certifications are also found in every country. Even the defunct Soviet Union had their own cert – the State Quality Mark of the USSR, which was used to certify that certain goods were of higher quality.

Product certification or product qualification is the process of certifying that a certain product has passed performance tests and quality assurance tests, and meets qualification criteria stipulated in contracts, regulations, or specifications (sometimes called "certification schemes" in the product certification industry).

Most product certification bodies (or product certifiers) are accredited to or aligned with ISO/IEC 17065 Conformity assessment – Requirements for bodies certifying products, processes, and services the international standard for ensuring competence in those organizations performing product, process and service certifications. The organizations that perform this accreditation are called Accreditation Bodies, and they themselves are assessed by international peers against the ISO 17011 standard.

The first was quality! Quality control and quality management have a long tradition: during the years, statistical quality control and quality management systems have been used to guarantee a high-quality level in every industrial production process. In the recent years, another tool for quality assurance has come to the fore namely, certification systems. Main feature of these systems is that all inspections are conducted by independent bodies (so-called third-party audit) grounded on standards laid down by well-known and accepted external organisations (standard owner). At the beginning there was the intention to create one standard for all economic sectors by establishing a general open-for-all certification scheme (ISO 9000). Unfortunately, this proved to be impossible. Today a large number of certification schemes can be identified. Instead of a one-for-all-standard more complex and industry-specific certification schemes are evolving throughout all sectors. Many economic approaches imply that both suppliers and buyers are fully informed about the commodities concerned. In fact, market activities are often characterised by far-reaching information deficits that impede the smooth functioning of markets.

Product certification gives the manufacturer the opportunity to have their product(s) certified by an independent, competent, and authorized third-party organization (Third-Party Declaration of Conformity) with regard to the fulfilment of product standards focusing on development/design, type testing and routine testing as well as quality management of manufacture. Certificates save the end customer (operating company) the time-consuming and challenging checking of the documents themselves which are submitted by the manufacturer to prove the conformity of the products to be purchased, giving them an independent status.

With the product certificate, the product manufacturer is attested the conformity of the product with the international standards and additional user specifications after a thorough assessment by the technically experienced personnel of the certification body. This concerns in particular the conformity of the fulfilment of the subsequent requirements (depending on the certification program selected):

- Requirements for type tests in European test laboratories accredited according to ISO/IEC 17025;
- Requirements regarding design and construction;
- Requirements regarding the routine tests;
- Requirements regarding a quality assurance system certified to ISO 9001.

A product might be verified to comply with a specification or stamped with a specification number. This does not, by itself, indicate that the item is fit for any particular use. The person or group of persons who own the certification scheme (i.e., engineers, trade unions, building code writers, government, industry, etc.) have the responsibility to consider the choice of available specifications, choose the correct ones, set qualification limits,

and enforce compliance with those limits. The end users of the product have the responsibility to use the item correctly. Products must be used in accordance with their listing for certification to be effective. Product certification is often required in sensitive industry and marketplace areas where a failure could have profound consequences, such as negatively affecting the health and welfare of the people or person using that product. For example, certification is stringent in aerospace applications, since the demands for low weight tend to lead to high stress on components, requiring appropriate metallurgy and accuracy in manufacturing. Other sensitive product area examples include food, pharmaceuticals, healthcare products, dangerous goods, electrical equipment and products that have RF emissions such as computers and cellular telephones.

Certified products are typically endorsed with a certification mark provided by the product certifier. Issuance of a certification mark is at the discretion of the individual product certifier. ISO 17065 does not require the product certifier to offer a certification mark in the event that a certificate is offered. When certification marks are issued and used on products, they are usually easy to see and enable users to track down the certification listings to determine the criteria that the product meets, and whether or not the listing is still active.

An active certification listing must minimally include indication of the following information:

- The specific product or type of product certified;
- The qualification standard that the product is judged to meet;
- The date of certification (and if applicable, its expiration).

Product certifiers may choose to include much more information than that listed above, but ISO 17065 specifies the bare minimum which must be made available regarding the certification status of a product.

These listings are typically used by an authority, such as a municipal building inspector, fire prevention officer, or electrical inspector, to compare the product's use or installation with the intent of the rating by testing. In order to comply with the code, the product listing must be "active", as products and companies can become "de-listed" due to re-testing showing that a product no longer meets qualification criteria, or a business decision by the manufacturer.

The International Accreditation Forum (IAF) has a listing of all recognized Accreditation Bodies whose accreditations to the ISO 17065 standard are deemed equivalent. From the IAF MLA informational page [13]: *"IAF is encouraging more of its members to join the MLA as soon as they have passed a rigorous evaluation process to ensure that their accreditation programs are of world standard. The consequence of joining the IAF MLA is that conformity assessment certificates issued, within the scope of the IAF MLA, by conformity assessment bodies accredited by any one of the members of the IAF MLA will be recognised in the world wide IAF program."*

Most countries only have a single Accreditation Body representing their economy in the IAF MLA. The two exceptions are the United States with American National Standards Institute (ANSI), American National Standards Institute - American Society for Quality National Accreditation Board (ANAB, a subdivision of ANSI), American Association for Laboratory Accreditation (A2LA), and International Accreditation Service (IAS) as signatory members, and United Accreditation Foundation as Full Member of IAF (International Accreditation Forum); and Korea which is represented by Korea Accreditation Board (KAB) and Korean Accreditation System (KAS).

Each Accreditation Body is required to keep a listing of those organizations it accredits, as well as a Scope of Accreditation which details the activities that the organizations can perform, whether that be testing, inspection, or product certification. Accreditation Bodies routinely audit the Product Certifiers whom they have accredited in order to determine if the performance or actions of the organization have changed and do not meet the requirements of the Accreditation Body and the International Standards they are to conform to.

4.2 Steps to product certification

WHY DO WE NEED PRODUCT CERTIFICATION?

The role of the product certification is to:

- assist clients and consumers to differentiate products in the marketplace and make informed purchasing decisions;
- give consumers more relevant assurance that the product concerned consistently meet the quality requirements of a reference standard or normative document;

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- allow the manufacturer/supplier to provide more clear indication to their customers that their ability of maintaining their product consistently conform to the quality requirement of a reference standard or normative document;
- supplement ISO9001 certification or other certification scheme, with specified control on operations and test regime for a particular product;
- provide a unified acceptance criterion for specifiers to put in specification for certain product other than simply performance requirements, which may only refer to test results of single or small number of specimens.

A product certification scheme process conducted by an impartial third party (Product Certification Body) to certify a product with the applied Certification Scope, based on a Product Certification Scheme developed, maintained and periodically reviewed by its Owner after evaluation of:

- the quality management system of the design and manufacturing processes;
- conformity of the product's characteristics to quality requirements in a reference standard/normative document.

A comparison between ISO 9001 certification and product certification is presented briefly in Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison between ISO 9001 certification and product certification.

Content/requirements	ISO 9001	Product certification
Reference standards	ISO 9001:2015	Product Certification Scheme established under the guidelines of ISO17067:2013
Focus	Quality Management System	Product Conformity
Objectives	To enhance customer satisfaction by meeting customer requirements and improve its overall performance and provide a sound basis for sustainable development initiatives.	To give interested parties the confidence regarding fulfilment of a product conforming to specified requirements. To allow suppliers to demonstrate to the market that their product has been attested to fulfil specified requirements by an impartial third party body.
Meeting the requirements of ISO 9001	Yes	Yes
Meeting the requirements in relevant Product Conformity Certification Scheme (PCCS)	No	Yes
Quality Requirements for Product/Service	No	Yes (refer to national or regional standards, like European standards)
Requirements for design, manufacturing and quality control processes	Determined by the organization itself	Yes (in particular for initial type testing & production control testing)
Audit testing	Not necessary	Mandatory! Sampling frequency and test items are stipulated in PCCS
Qualification and/or experience requirement(s) for technical representative in organization	Generally specified (Clause 7.2 Competence)	Yes for some PCCSs

The process for certification of a product is summed up in four steps (Figure 6).

- Application (including testing of the product).
- Evaluation (does the test data indicate that the product meets qualification criteria?).
- Decision (does a second review of the product application concur with the evaluation?).
- Surveillance (does the product in the marketplace continue to meet qualification criteria?).

In many instances, prior to applying for certification, a product supplier will send a product to a testing laboratory (some certification schemes require the product to be sent out for testing by the product certifier instead). When

the product to be certified is received at the testing laboratory, it is tested in accordance with the laboratory's internal procedures and with the methods listed in the test standards specified by the certification scheme. The resulting data collected by the testing laboratory is then forwarded either back to the manufacturer, or directly to the product certifier.

Products often need periodic recertification, also known as surveillance. This requirement is typically identified within the certification scheme that the product is certified to. Certification bodies may require product suppliers to perform some sort of surveillance activity, such as pulling sample products from the marketplace for testing, to maintain their "listed" or "certified" status.

Some certification schemes, or the product certifiers that operate those Schemes, may require that the product supplier operate a Quality Management System registered to ISO 9000, or that the testing be performed by a laboratory accredited to ISO 17025. The decision to set these requirements is most often made by the person or group which owns the Certification Scheme.

Figure 6. Certification scheme for a product

ISO/IEC 17067:2013, and its predecessor ISO/IEC Guide 67:2004 have been in use for more than 20 years as guidance for product certification schemes. This guidance proved especially valuable when ISO/IEC 17065:2012 set requirements for product, process, and service certification bodies but stated that “does not set requirements for schemes and how they are developed and is not intended to restrict the role or choice of scheme owners.” The examples of product certification schemes (the well-known “Types”) in ISO/IEC 17067 have been used to characterize product certification schemes in both regulatory and voluntary contexts. This context is briefly presented in following.

The certification program can be defined as a certification system related to specified products, to which the same specified requirements, specific rules and procedures apply. Certain certification programs may include preliminary test of the product and pre-license inspection or assessment of quality management systems at the production site, followed by surveillance including periodic testing or inspection of samples taken from production and/or the market. Other programs consist of a preliminary test and surveillance tests, and still others may include only product type testing, limited to testing the provided sample.

For an easy and unambiguous recognition of differences between individual certification programs, PN-EN ISO/IEC 17067 introduced the concept of program type, digitally highlighted, assigning to each of them a specific share of individual functions and conformity assessment activities in the product certification system.

Types of certification programs for products have been classified from 1 to 5, whereas the type 6 program applies only in process certification. The lists of conformity assessment activities that are to be performed in a given certification program of a given type are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Type of product certification scheme EN ISO/IEC 17067 [14]⁵

Conformity assessment functions and activities within product certification schemes	Type of product certification scheme *					
	1a	1b	2	3	4	5
Activities for issuing the certificate						
Product evaluation – type test acc.	X	X	X	X	X	X
Assessment of production- pre-license inspection in factory				X	X	X
Review	X	X	X	X	X	X
Decision on certification	X	X	X	X	X	X
Certification documents	X	X	X	X	X	X
Certificate of conformity	X	X	X	X	X	X
License – granting the right to use marks of conformity		X	X	X	X	X
Certification of a batch		X				
Surveillance after issuing a certificate						
Testing of samples from the open market			X		X	X
Testing of samples from the factory				X	X	X
Assessment of the production, the delivery of the service				X	X	X
Management system audits combined with random tests or inspections						X
*The program type 6 for processes has been omitted						

It can be seen that in all types of programs there is a product evaluation carried out by testing a product sample to demonstrate compliance with specified requirements.

In programs with the surveillance and certification of compliance of a batch, in addition to the certificate of conformity, a document entitling to use a certified certification mark for the certified product is issued. Such a document is called a license.

Scheme type 1a

In this scheme, one or more samples of the product are subject to the determination activities. A certificate of conformity or other statement of conformity (e.g., a letter) is issued for the product type, the characteristics of

⁵ Must take in consideration that ISO 17067:2013 is under revision.

In July 2023, ISO CASCO Members voted not just to revise ISO/IEC 17067, but to also expand its scope so that it provides guidance on all types of schemes, which potentially makes the revised ISO/IEC 17067 as foundationally important as ISO/IEC 17000.

which are detailed in the certificate or a document referred to in the certificate. Subsequent production items are not covered by the certification body's attestation of conformity.

Scheme type 1b

This scheme type involves the certification of a whole batch of products, following selection and determination as specified in the scheme. The proportion to be tested, which can include testing of all the units in the batch (100% testing), would be based, for example, on the homogeneity of the items in the batch and the application of sampling plan, where appropriate. If the outcome of determination, review and decision is positive, all items in the batch may be described as certified and may have a mark of conformity affixed, if that is included in the scheme.

This type of certification is preferred in cases required by law, periodic nature of production and also at the recipient's request.

Scheme type 2

In this program, the evaluation for the issuance of the certificate is limited to the product evaluation carried out by testing the product sample to demonstrate compliance with the specified requirements. The surveillance part of this scheme involves periodically taking samples of the product from the market and subjecting them to demonstration activities to check that items produced subsequent to the initial attestation fulfil the specified requirements. This program does not provide for the assessment of production. It is preferred if there is no possibility and need to carry out a factory inspection. Usually used for the certification of imported products and also in cases where legal provisions require entities to purchase equipment that has the appropriate attestations or certificates, e.g., equipment for schools and facilities.

Schemes types 3, 4 & 5

In these programs, unlike the other types, at the stage before the certificate is issued, the assessment of production process is carried out. The assessment of production, by pre-license factory inspection, is aimed at demonstrating compliance with the technical and organizational conditions guaranteeing the maintenance of repeatable production of products at the level confirmed by the type test of the product. In programs that include this action, there is always a surveillance function after issuing the certificate. The surveillance part covers both periodic sampling of products, for conducting control tests as well as periodic factory inspections, often referred to as routine inspections. Product inspection tests are performed to check whether products manufactured after the issuance of the certificate still meet the specified requirements. The purpose of the routine inspection is to confirm the maintenance of the proper production process at a level confirmed by a pre-license inspection.

It can be concluded that the certification carried out in this type of program not only confirms the conformity of the type of product identified with the specified requirements, but also gives a high degree of confidence that the subsequent manufactured products (from current production) also meet these requirements.

4.3 CE marking of construction products

CE marking has been introduced by the COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 93/68/EEC of 22 July 1993 amending Directives 87/404/EEC (simple pressure vessels), 88/378/EEC (safety of toys), 89/106/EEC (construction products), 89/336/EEC (electromagnetic compatibility), 89/392/EEC (machinery), 89/686/EEC (personal protective equipment), 90/384/EEC (non-automatic weighing instruments), 90/385/EEC (active implantable medicinal devices), 90/396/EEC (appliances burning gaseous fuels), 91/263/EEC (telecommunications terminal equipment), 92/42/EEC (new hot-water boilers fired with liquid or gaseous fuels), 93/42/EEC (medical devices) and 73/23/EEC (electrical equipment designed for use within certain voltage limits).

Documents from the European Commission and European Parliament reveal that it was during efforts to relaunch regional market integration in the 1980s through a "new approach" to standardization that the CE marking process was first developed. The Commission saw standards as a tool to liberalize markets and shape the business environment of the region. As it began to develop directives for product standards, however, the Commission quickly realized that its standardization program would need urgent reform if the European Community (EC) was to complete a Single Market by its 1992 deadline. It proposed a streamlined, modular "global approach" and, through the European Parliament's Committee on Economic and Monetary Affairs and Industrial Policy, sought the input of the business groups it hoped would embrace the CE marking process.

In 1990, Business associations with significant interests in European markets like UNICE and the EC Committee of the American Chamber of Commerce were asked to comment on the modules, assessment scheme, and CE mark criteria of the Commission's Global Approach. Their responses reveal broad business preferences not for less regulation and oversight, but rather for even greater clarity on the CE marking process, for equitable access to product testing and certification for companies based outside the EC, and for stronger enforcement of CE mark violators. Importantly, though, small firms and state-owned enterprises feared the costs of conformity assessment and the loss of preferential state regulation. Archival documents also show that these exchanges between business associations and European institutions were not a case of "regulatory capture;" the Council initially ignored the recommendations of the groups consulted. When it did decide on CE marking on the eve of the Maastricht Treaty's signing in 1991, the European Council took a rather protectionist approach by restricting assessment and certification access in third countries, thereby favouring European firms over those importing goods to the EC from places like Japan and the United States [11].

The added value of CE marking is that all EU countries must allow the selling of construction products bearing the CE mark. This means that public authorities cannot ask for any additional marks or certificates, let alone additional testing. Therefore, a manufacturer or the distributors of the product can trade a product in any country of the European Internal Market with the same documentation. Together with the Declaration of Performance this will also help your customers and final users to check the performance of the product and compare it with other products under the same technical approach.

The CE marking contains certain essential information about the product and provides a link to other additional documents which also contain important information. The CE marking is compulsory for most construction products to sell them on the European Internal Market. For the rest it is not compulsory but possible under certain rules.

When you want to know if the CE marking of your product is compulsory the first step is to go to the Official Journal of the European Union and search for the last update of the publication of titles and references of harmonised standards. Then you must check the product against the titles of standards available to see if their product is covered by any of them.

When the product is not in the scope of any harmonised standard a manufacturer can voluntarily CE mark their product but must check first if it is covered by one of the existing European Assessment Documents (EAD) or a European Technical Assessment (ETA). The list with documents can be checked on the website of the European Commission in the area called NANDOIV (New Approach Notified and Designated Organisations). There is a specific page which includes the list of European Assessment Documents.

Derogations from mandatory CE-marking and Declaration of Performance

Sometimes a manufacturer can obtain a 'derogation' (an exemption) from the CE-marking requirement. The exceptions are cases where the product is individually manufactured or custom-made for a given use or where the manufacturing of the product must maintain traditional processes to guarantee the conservation of officially protected works (heritage / historical works etc.).

CE marking does not only consist of affixing a label to the product – manufacturers must carry out many tasks to complete the process of CE marking. The process is described in brief below.

1. Before starting and during the whole process the following documents are needed:
 - a. (For the CEN route) – The harmonised standard or standards applicable to the product. Sometimes the harmonised standard contains references to other standards (test methods, tabulated values, etc.) that may be important.
 - b. (For the EOTA route) – The European assessment document or documents applicable to the product. Sometimes the European assessment document contains references to standards that may be important.
2. Development of internal quality procedures, sometimes collaboration of external laboratories or service providers will be needed. The manufacturer is responsible for assessing product performance and putting in place factory production control. The continuous assessment results and factory production control allows the manufacturer to check that the performance does not change over time. The legal terminology used to describe this is "assessment and verification of constancy of performance" (AVCP2) and the third-party verifier or verifiers are the Notified Bodies. The assessment of the product is done by defining the value of a list of characteristics called essential characteristics.
3. The annex ZA of the harmonised standards and in the European Assessment Documents (EAD) gives the necessary information. The list can be different for each intended use and in the case of a product with more than one intended use the list should cover the characteristics linked to each of them. The list also includes

the AVCP system for each essential characteristic. Depending on the AVCP system a manufacturer may need one or several Notified Bodies to carry out tasks related to it.

4. Assessment and verification of constancy of performance systems (AVCP systems). The list of essential characteristics relevant for the product must be compared with the manufacturer procedures to declare the performance of each essential characteristic, such as test methods, tabulated values, etc. The AVCP system applicable to each essential characteristic will require in some cases that a Notified Body performs some additional tasks. In the following figure the manufacturer and Notified Bodies tasks that must be carried out depending on the AVCP system are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. AVCP system [12]

If all the product characteristics come under AVCP system 4 it will not need to contract a Notified Body. When they are covered by system 3 the product must be tested by a Notified Body (in this case a notified laboratory) that can be different for each essential characteristic. If they are under system 1, 1+ or 2+ the Notified Body will collaborate with the manufacturer during the assessment and will do some tasks in the manufacturing plant.

Member States have different demands in place for the essential characteristics of products used in each country. A manufacturer may also decide that some essential characteristics are not relevant for the product, if they are not requested by the customers.

In this case where the manufacturer has decided not to declare specific characteristics should write “no performance determined” using the acronym “NPD”. The use of “NPD” is possible following certain conditions:

- For products following the CEN route you must declare the performance of at least one of the essential characteristics.
- Sometime, for certain essential characteristics, it could be that declaring NPD is not allowed.

For the manufacturers who use EOTA route, the first step is to contact the Technical Assessment Body that will then carry out the tasks according to the European Assessment Document. The Technical Assessment Body will issue a document for you called European Technical Assessment (ETA) that will be necessary in the next steps.

5. For some essential characteristics, there is no need to do any assessment because a generic value or declaration is accepted at European level. In this case the European Commission publishes a legal act containing this information. In order to benefit from this option, a manufacturer will need to develop a document explaining that the product is covered by this legal act. This document is officially called “appropriate technical documentation”. If the essential characteristic is under AVCP system 1 or 1+ the Notified Body must verify this document.
 - Background documents. After the assessment of the essential characteristics the manufacturer should have the documents shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Background documents for production process [12]

6. Once the assessment is finished, the manufacturer have to assign a code to the product (usually a code consisting of the commercial name of the product, an internal code linked to the manufacturing process and the date the assessment of the product was done). The name of this code is “unique identification code of the product type” and it is linked to the sort of product are manufacturing and to the performance of its essential characteristics. When the manufacturer develops a new product it have to assign a new unique ID-code to it and in case the performance of a product changes the manufacturer would also have to change the code.

Each time a manufacturer develops a new product it will have to repeat all the tasks including, if necessary, contracting a Notified Body and a technical assessment body.

4.4 Certification scheme for wood products

4.4.1 Forest certifications and custody certification tracks

Forest certification first arose in response to concerns about the preservation of the world’s forests. It developed because of the 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) in Brazil, which defined ‘sustainable development’ as a common goal of human development.

The preamble of the ‘Forest Principles’ – one of the five outcome documents – stated that “*forests are essential to economic development and the maintenance of all forms of life.*” But governments were unable to agree on the specifics of sustainable forest management at the UN level, and so forest certification arose as a process and a mechanism to bring people together to define it.

Choosing wood from certified forests means that it is traceable throughout the processing, transport, and use. This transparency can give you the confidence that you are truly using a renewable material sourced in a responsible and environmentally conscious way that does not damage habitats or have a negative environmental impact. Sustainably sourced wood can be more expensive than wood that does not comply with national requirements and international certifications. That’s due in part to the additional steps that PEFC or FSC certified timber needs to undergo to ensure that it is harvested in a responsible manner. Another reason is that it is produced in smaller quantities instead of ‘overcutting’ which aggravates deforestation and subsequently soil erosion, flooding, CO₂ emissions, etc. In addition, sustainable timber is sourced and processed using fair labour, which excludes child and forced labour.

Forest certification is a voluntary, market-based instrument, implemented through two separate but linked processes namely, sustainable forest management certification and chain of custody certification. Sustainable forest management certification assures that forests are managed in line with challenging environmental, social and economic requirements.

Forest management certification process [15]

Decision and contract. The operator determines the overall investment needed to fulfil the requirements of certification and the benefits that might be expected. On this basis, it decides whether certification is in its interests, and, if so, which certification scheme and certifier would be most appropriate. The operator and the selected certifier enter a formal contract.

Preliminary audit. Once contracted, the certifier checks relevant documentation to ensure that the documentation requirements of the certification standard are met.

On-site assessment. A team of experts selected by the certifier undertakes a detailed on-site assessment, checking forest operations and consulting with relevant stakeholders, including employees and local people. The team produces a report on the performance of the operator according to the relevant standards.

Adjustments. Depending on the findings of the team of experts, the operator may need to adjust its operation to ensure that it meets the certification standards; these adjustments are often referred to as “*major corrective actions*”. The team of experts may also recommend other actions to improve performance that should be taken during the certification period, often called “*minor corrective actions*”.

Issuance of certification. When the major corrective actions have been taken to the satisfaction of the certifier, the operator is issued with a forest management certificate. Such certificates are valid for several years.

Verification audits. To ensure compliance with the standard over the validation period of the certificate and to guarantee that any specified minor corrective actions are taken, most certification schemes require an annual verification audit, which may include inspection visits by the certifier and may result in new recommendations for corrective actions. In the case of non-compliance with requirements, certification may be suspended.

Renewal. To renew the certification, a new audit is undertaken. The above steps are depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Forest management certification

Chain of custody certification tracks forest-based products from sustainable sources to the final product. It demonstrates that each step of the supply chain is closely monitored through independent auditing to ensure that unsustainable sources are excluded.

For the BIOBUILD project the most important certification for wood products is custody certification tracks.

Chain-of-custody certification

Chain-of-custody certification ensures that wood, wood based materials or non-wood forest products contained in an item or product line originates from certified forests. It allows companies to label their products, which in turn enables consumers to identify and choose products that support responsible forest management (Figure

10). In the PEFC system, chain-of-custody certification is rolled into the forest management certificate; under the FSC, the two certificate types have separate standards but can be combined in a joint certificate where applicable (e.g., when an operator is vertically integrated).

There are three methods for tracing the origin of forest-based products (Figure 11). One involves a strict separation of certified and non-certified raw materials in all phases of the production process. In the other two, the certifiers allow the mixing of certified and non-certified raw materials or reclaimed forest-based materials under controlled procedures to avoid incorporating material from illegal harvesting. Chain-of-custody certification can be obtained by an individual company, a group of operations composed of several smaller enterprises, and larger companies operating at multiple locations. For a product to qualify for chain-of-custody certification, all entities along the supply chain must possess a certificate. All chain-of-custody certification procedures require common, centrally administered and monitored control and reporting systems that allow certifiers to evaluate participating operations or sites using a sampling approach [15].

Figure 10. Chain of custody ideal flux

Figure 11. Chain of custody methods

4.4.1.1 PEFC certification

In 1999, small- and family forest owners from Europe joined together to create a forest certification system that would enable them to demonstrate their excellence in sustainable forest management. Now, PEFC is the largest

forest certification system in the world. The Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) is an international, non-profit, non-governmental organization which promotes sustainable forest management through independent third-party certification.

PEFC was founded in 1999, in France, as a response to the specific requirements of small- and family forest owners, led by the Confederation of European Forest Owners (CEPF), as an international umbrella organization providing independent assessment, endorsement and recognition of national forest certification systems. The first forest owners were able to achieve PEFC certification in 2000, as PEFC endorsed the first national forest certification systems (in Finland, Sweden, Norway, Germany and Austria). Two years later, in 2002, was published the first PEFC Chain of Custody guidelines, enabling the appearance of PEFC-certified products on the market. In 2009, PEFC expanded into two more continents, Gabon and Malaysia, where the national forest certification systems achieved endorsement.

PEFC became the first global forest certification system to introduce social aspects in chain of custody certification in 2010, and a few years later in 2013, the Chain of Custody standard was aligned with the European Union Timber Regulation (EUTR).

It published the edition of the sustainable forest management benchmark standard in 2018, extending the impact of PEFC certification beyond forests and enhancing its contribution to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The revised versions of three vital PEFC international standards governing chain of custody certification, trademark use, and conformity assessment were published in 2020.

PEFC responds to the need of a mechanism enabling the independent development of national standards tailored to the political, economic, social, environmental and cultural realities of the respective countries, while at the same time ensuring compliance with internationally-accepted requirements and global recognition.

The construction industry faces specific challenges when proving that the timber specified and supplied for individual construction projects is from certified sustainable sources. Chain of custody certification is not always the most efficient option for these short-term projects involving different, uncertified contractors.

PEFC solved this challenge with chain of custody certification for specified projects, or 'project certification', a mechanism for gaining independent verification of the use of certified timber in a one-off project with a limited duration.

PEFC only recognizes forests certified to standards that have been reviewed and endorsed by PEFC. PEFC's certification standards are based on the principles of sustainable forest management, which include protecting biodiversity, ensuring the rights and welfare of forest workers and local communities, and promoting responsible forest management practices.

National forest certification systems that wish to be recognized by PEFC are required to set standards keeping with the requirements of ISO/IEC Guide 59:2019. National standards must be developed by so-called National Governing Bodies, and meet requirements for transparency, consultation and decision-making by consensus. These guidelines also outline processes for revising and amending standards and provide those who utilise the standard with the security of future certainty.

All PEFC-endorsed standards have been subjected to public review during their development. National forest certification systems wanting to obtain PEFC endorsement are subject to an independent assessment to ensure that it meets the PEFC requirements for the standards development process, public review and forest management requirements. The consultant's report is reviewed by an independent Panel of Experts and the PEFC Board, and if satisfactory, the new standard is approved by the PEFC members as a PEFC-endorsed standard. To ensure the independence of the certification bodies, they are not accredited by PEFC itself, but by a national accreditation agency.

PEFC members are organised in economic, environmental and social membership chambers.

In line with its commitment to transparency, PEFC makes its entire documentation of national forest certification system, including the independent assessments, publicly available. Information about all issued certificates, including information about suspended, withdrawn and expired certificates, is publicly available on the PEFC website.

The PEFC's criteria for SFM (Sustainable Forest Management) standards [16]:

- Criterion 1: Maintenance and appropriate enhancement of forest resources and their contribution to the global carbon cycle.
- Criterion 2: Maintenance of forest ecosystem health and vitality.
- Criterion 3: Maintenance and encouragement of productive functions of forests (wood and non-wood).
- Criterion 4: Maintenance, conservation and appropriate enhancement of biological diversity in forest ecosystems.
- Criterion 5: Maintenance and appropriate enhancement of protective functions in forest management (notably soil and water).
- Criterion 6: Maintenance of other socioeconomic functions and conditions.
- Criterion 7: Compliance with legal requirements.

Countries with PEFC endorsed national certification systems are Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Gabon, Germany, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malaysia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Romania, Thailand, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay and Viet Nam.

Forest Stewardship Council is the main alternative forest certification system. Mutual recognition of FSC and PEFC certified material in the chain of custody has not yet happened. However, FSC and PEFC use the same forest management standard in countries such as the United Kingdom, Switzerland and Norway; Malaysia has submitted its timber certification scheme for PEFC endorsement that is largely based on FSC principles and criteria.

Several environmental non-governmental organizations, such as The Wilderness Society, Greenpeace and FERN⁶ have criticized the PEFC. For example, Greenpeace does not believe that the alternatives to the FSC, including PEFC, can ensure responsible forest management.

4.4.1.2 FSC certification

Forest Stewardship Council (FSC), was founded in 1993 as a voluntary certification for sustainable forestry, promoting environmentally sound, socially beneficial, and economically viable management of the world's forests. Nowadays, FSC has the most extensive certified supply chain network, enabling connections between markets and sustainable forestry – including over 200 million hectares of forest managed according to FSC standards.

In 1994, the membership organization FSC Asociación Civil (AC) was established as a legal entity in Mexico, in Oaxaca by groups from 25 countries. In the same year, the first certified product, a wooden spatula, became available in the United Kingdom.

In 1997 the first General Assembly took place and the first FSC National Standard (NFSS) was endorsed in Sweden. In just two years, 10 million hectares of forest were certified to FSC standards. In 2003 FSC secretariat moved from Oaxaca, Mexico, to Bonn, Germany.

The first Standards for small or low-intensity managed forests (SLIMF) came into effect in 2004. The Accreditation Services International GmbH (ASI) was created in 2005, to manage the FSC accreditation programme.

In 2020 the FSC Core Labour Requirements, based on the principles of the International Labour Organization core conventions, were embedded into the CoC standards. Today FSC has over 200 million FSC-certified areas and more than 50 000 CoC certificates.

FSC forest management certification confirms that the forest is being managed in a way that preserves biological diversity and benefits the lives of local people and workers, while ensuring it sustains economic viability. FSC-certified forests are managed to strict environmental, social and economic standards. There are ten principles that any forest operation must adhere to before it can receive FSC forest management certification. These principles cover a broad range of issues, from maintaining high conservation values to

⁶ Fern (also Stichting Fern) is a Dutch foundation created in 1995 [2]. It is an international Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) set up to keep track of the European Union's (EU) involvement in forests and coordinate NGO activities at the European level. Fern works to protect forests and the rights of people who depend on them.

community relations and workers' rights, as well as monitoring the environmental and social impacts of the forest management. The **10 FSC Principles** are [17]:

- Principle 1: Compliance with laws
- Principle 2: Workers Rights and Employment Conditions
- Principle 3: Indigenous Peoples' Rights
- Principle 4: Community Relations
- Principle 5: Benefits from the forest
- Principle 6: Environmental Values and Impacts
- Principle 7: Management Planning
- Principle 8: Monitoring and assessment
- Principle 9: High Conservation Value
- Principle 10: Implementation of Management Activities

FSC chain of custody certification verifies that FSC-certified material has been identified and separated from non-certified and uncontrolled material as it makes its way along the supply chain, from the forest to the market.

Any company involved in the processing or transformation of FSC-certified products (e.g., manufacturing, repackaging, pack-splitting, relabelling, and cutting to size or adding other forest-based components to the product) must be FSC certified to apply an FSC label to their products and/or sell them with a FSC claim.

FSC owns five registered trademarks, i.e., the name "Forest Stewardship Council", the abbreviation "FSC", the FSC 'tick-tree' logo and the full and text-only 'Forests For All Forever' brand marks. The FSC trademarks can be used by FSC certificate holders and FSC promotional licence holders. They can also be used for educational and research purposes and by the media. FSC's tick-tree logo is a key part of the FSC labels, which can be found on millions of products and items of packaging around the world. The differences between PEFC and FSC are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. FSC vs. PEFC: two different approaches [18]

4.4.1.3 FLEGT license

FLEGT licences are documents issued by timber-producing countries that have ratified a Voluntary Partnership Agreement with the EU. The licences confirm that timber or timber products comply fully with the relevant laws of the country of export. FLEGT-licensed timber and timber products are considered to comply with the

requirements of the EU Timber Regulation, which prohibits EU importers and EU timber producers from placing illegally harvested timber and timber products on the EU market. EU importers therefore do not need to undertake further due diligence on FLEGT-licensed timber.

For a VPA country to issue FLEGT licences, it must put in place a timber legality assurance system and other measures outlined in the VPA. When fully operational, VPA timber legality assurance systems are robust and credible. Legality assurance systems control supply chains, verify legal compliance and are independently audited. The systems are built on practical definitions of legality that have been developed through participatory processes involving stakeholders from government, the private sector and civil society [19].

FLEGT licences therefore indicate that products comply with a broad range of laws and regulations in the partner country, such as a selection of those relating to forest management, environmental aspects, labour rights, community benefits, import and export procedures, and payments of fees and taxes.

FLEGT Competent Authorities are the authorities in EU Member States responsible for verifying FLEGT licences, as set out in the EU FLEGT Regulation.

In many EU Member States, a single Competent Authority is responsible for both the EU Timber Regulation and the FLEGT Regulation. Other Member States divide responsibilities for implementing the EUTR and the FLEGT Regulation between two Competent Authorities.

4.4.1.4 O.L.B. – Origine et Légalité des Bois

For about twenty years, the problems of illegal timber have been at the heart of the concerns of wood supply policies, both private and public. Governmental and intergovernmental organizations consider this threat very seriously by imposing strict measures to remedy inappropriate practices.

At the level of operators in the timber industry, these concerns translate into a growing need for guarantees regarding the legality of wood purchases, an element that cannot be dissociated from knowledge of the geographical origin.

Bureau Veritas Certification has developed the OLB (Origin and Legality of Wood) system, following requests from customers wishing to obtain an official, third-party certificate concerning the legality of their wood [20]. The system is based on:

- a certificate intended for forest operators/managers;
- a chain of custody certificate intended for manufacturers and traders.

The timber legality certificate is based on compliance with the standard for the certification of forestry companies. The document presents the provisions to be met in order to comply with the laws on the management and exploitation of wood, employment and safety of people, and respect for the environment. It also largely addresses issues of traceability of wood within the company up to sale or initial processing.

The certification of timber processing and trading companies is based on compliance with the chain of custody standard. This document presents the provisions to be met to obtain the right to use the OLB mark on the companies' products. OLB is an international system based on:

- a strict and complete legality;
- a traceability requirement adapted to forestry companies;
- a simple and effective timber tracking (chain of custody).

The key steps of the OLB approach are as follows:

- Establishment of a contract specific to the company;
- Pre-audit (optional): a gap analysis and diagnosis of the current situation in relation to the requirements of the standard;
- Initial audit: to verify the requirements of the standard;
- Certification decision and award of the certificate;
- Surveillance audits to verify the persistence of the system's compliance;
- After a period of 5 years, renewal of the certificate. At each audit stage, a full report is given to the client and the audit team monitor the certificate throughout its validity.

4.4.1.5 Preferred by Nature Certification

Preferred by Nature is an international non-profit organization, dedicated to promoting sustainable land management and responsible business practices. They provide certification, consulting, and advisory services to help businesses and organizations enhance their environmental sustainability. The Preferred by Nature Certification programme refers to forests management and nurture farms.

It offers two options to cater to the customer unique needs:

- Full certification: Preferred by Nature Certification against the Sustainability Framework, covering environmental, social and economic aspects of your operations.
- Regulatory scope option: Streamline the certification process by focusing on specific regulatory indicators, including those within the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR), demonstrating alignment efficiently. Could be also integrate the Preferred by Nature Certification as an add-on to other existing certificates an organization have, making the entire certification effort more efficient and cost-effective.

Preferred for Nature Certification attesting:

- DDS (Due Diligence System) performance;
- Mitigation of the risk of illegality.

Preferred for Nature Certification uses 1 universal standard and 2 annexes:

- DDS assessment requirements;
- Annex 1: Forest legal compliance assessment;
- Annex 2: Legal compliance in the supply chain.

However, this certification mark is not a guarantee of forest legality.

4.4.1.6 SCS Legal Harvest Certification

Increasing awareness of the impacts of deforestation and their contribution to climate change are fuelling oversight by governments and scrutiny by NGOs. SCS Legal Harvest Verification provides third-party confirmation of the legal right to harvest, process, transport, and export wood products. The verification is available to forest managers, sawmills, pulp mills, secondary manufacturers, traders and distributors, retailers, and others in wood products supply chains. It integrates key aspects of wood product legality requirements from around the world into one standard, so you can be assured that your company has the documentation and evidence needed to uphold the traceability and legality of your timber sourcing.

SCS is a leading third-party certification body with 40 years of experience certifying environmental and sustainability claims. It is focused on customer service and can contract with companies, deploy auditors to the field and make certification decisions faster than the competition. SCS Legal Harvest forestry certifications pre-date the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC). As one of the FSC's original 3 certifiers, SCS is one of the most respected certification bodies throughout the world for integrity, scientific rigor, and true independence. With auditors throughout the globe, it has certified more than 3000 wood product companies worldwide.

SCS' Legal Harvest™ verification is applicable for Forest Management, Chain of Custody and Multi-Sites. Through its focus on timber traceability and legality verification, the scheme helps companies mitigate supply chain risks, reinforce investor and customer confidence, and maintain a competitive market presence. Verification confirms the legal right to harvest, process, transport, and export wood products, no matter where the operations are located.

Legal Harvest is applicable to Forest Management and Chain of Custody operations, as well as groups and entities and multi-sites. The scheme helps companies demonstrate compliance with the US Lacey Act, European Union Timber Regulation, Australia Illegal Logging Prohibition Act, and other regulations that require the legal procurement of wood products. Verification helps companies mitigate supply chain risks, reinforce investor and customer confidence, and maintain a competitive market presence.

4.5 Certification of sustainable construction products & indoor air quality

Indoor air quality (IAQ) is the air quality within buildings and structures. Poor indoor air quality due to indoor air pollution is known to affect the health, comfort, and well-being of building occupants. It has also been linked to sick building syndrome, respiratory issues, reduced productivity, and impaired learning in schools. Common pollutants of indoor air include: second hand tobacco smoke, air pollutants from indoor combustion, radon, moulds and other allergens, carbon monoxide, volatile organic compounds, legionella and other bacteria, asbestos fibres, carbon dioxide, ozone and particulates. We spend about 90% of our time indoors. IAQ affects everyone, especially the most vulnerable - children, the elderly, and people with health conditions like asthma and heart disease.

IAQ is evaluated through collection of air samples, monitoring human exposure to pollutants, analysis of building surfaces, and computer modelling of air flow inside buildings. IAQ is part of indoor environmental quality (IEQ), along with other factors that exert an influence on physical and psychological aspects of life indoors (e.g., lighting, visual quality, acoustics, and thermal comfort).

There are many sources of indoor air pollution. For our project IAQ generated from building materials is the one of the important sources of pollution that must be taken in consideration:

- **Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)** include a variety of chemicals, some of which may have short- and long-term adverse health effects. VOCs include a variety of chemicals, some of which may have short- and long-term adverse health effects. Concentrations of many VOCs are consistently higher indoors (up to ten times higher) than outdoors. VOCs are emitted by a wide array of products numbering in the thousands. VOCs presenting health hazards include benzene, formaldehyde, tetrachloroethylene and trichloroethylene.

VOCs are emitted by thousands of indoor products. Examples include: paints, varnishes, waxes and lacquers, paint strippers, cleaning and personal care products, pesticides, building materials and furnishings, office equipment such as copiers and printers, correction fluids and carbonless copy paper, graphics and craft materials including glues and adhesives, permanent markers, and photographic solutions. Testing emissions from building materials used indoors has become increasingly common for floor coverings, paints, and many other important indoor building materials and finishes.

Several initiatives aim to reduce indoor air contamination by limiting VOC emissions from products. There are regulations in France and in Germany, and numerous voluntary ecolabels and rating systems containing low VOC emissions criteria such as EMICODE⁷, M1⁸, Blue Angel⁹ and Indoor Air Comfort in Europe, as well as California Standard CDPH Section 01350¹⁰ and several others in the US. Due to these initiatives an increasing number of low-emitting products became available to purchase.

- **Asbestos fibres.** Many common building materials used before 1975 contain asbestos, such as some floor tiles, ceiling tiles, shingles, fireproofing, heating systems, pipe wrap, taping muds, mastics, and other insulation materials. Normally, significant releases of asbestos fibre do not occur unless the building materials are disturbed, such as by cutting, sanding, drilling, or building remodelling. Removal of asbestos-containing materials is not always optimal because the fibres can be spread into the air during the removal process. A management program for intact asbestos-containing materials is often recommended instead.
- **Biological contaminants** include bacteria, viruses, animal dander and cat saliva, house dust, mites, cockroaches, and pollen. There are many sources of these pollutants.

⁷ The EMICODE® classification system allows consumers and craftsmen to compare and evaluate the emission characteristics of flooring installation and construction products. Since EMICODE® was introduced in 1997, more than 14 000 products from all over the world have been awarded the EMICODE® label. It offers consumers, craftsmen and architects' guidance to decide which materials offer maximum safety from indoor air pollution, guarantee optimum health protection and high environmental compatibility [21].

⁸ The Finnish M1 Emission Classification of Building Materials has successfully helped to improve indoor air quality for almost 30 years. The M1 Emission Classification, introduced in 1996, was created to promote the development and use of low-emitting building materials, fixed furniture, and office furniture [22].

⁹ The Blue Angel has been the ecolabel of the German Federal Government for more than 45 years. It is an independent and credible label that sets stringent standards for environmentally friendly products and services. The Blue Angel is the guide for purchasing.

¹⁰ The State of California developed the California Standard Section 01350 specification to cover key environmental performance issues related to the selection and handling of building materials. It is the most popular US standard for evaluating and restricting VOC emissions for indoor air.

- Mould and other allergens. Occupants in buildings can be exposed to fungal spores, cell fragments, or mycotoxins which can arise from a host of means, but there are two common classes: a) excess moisture induced growth of mould colonies and b) natural substances released into the air such as animal dander and plant pollen.[23]
- Mould growth can be inhibited by keeping surfaces at conditions that are further from condensation, with relative humidity levels below 75%. This usually translates to a relative humidity of indoor air below 60%, in agreement with the guidelines for thermal comfort that recommend a relative humidity of 40-60 %.
- Legionella. Legionnaires' disease is caused by a waterborne bacterium Legionella that grows best in slow-moving or still, warm water. The primary route of exposure is through the creation of an aerosol effect, most commonly from evaporative cooling towers or showerheads. A common source of Legionella in commercial buildings is from poorly placed or maintained evaporative cooling towers, which often release water in an aerosol which may enter nearby ventilation intakes. Legionella is a parasite of protozoans such as amoeba, and thus requires conditions suitable for both organisms. The bacterium forms a biofilm which is resistant to chemical and antimicrobial treatments, including chlorine.
- Other bacteria. Airborne bacteria. There are many bacteria of health significance found in indoor air and on indoor surfaces. The role of microbes in the indoor environment is increasingly studied using modern gene-based analysis of environmental samples.
- Houseplants together with the medium in which they are grown can reduce components of indoor air pollution, particularly volatile organic compounds (VOC) such as benzene, toluene, and xylene. Plants remove CO₂ and release oxygen and water, although the quantitative impact for house plants is small. The interest in using potted plants for removing VOCs was sparked by a 1989 NASA study conducted in sealed chambers designed to replicate the environment on space stations.

4.5.1 Floor Score Certificate

FloorScore is the most recognized indoor air quality (IAQ) certification standard for hard surface flooring materials, adhesives, and underlayment. Developed by SCS with the Resilient Floor Covering Institute (RFCI), a leading industry trade association of flooring manufacturers and suppliers, it qualifies for many green building schemes including LEED v4.1, WELL, BREEAM, CHPS, and Green Globes.

FloorScore® Private Label certification is available to customers of certified manufacturers to allow re-branding of SCS certified products under the customers' company name. Customers will undergo a Private Label certification assessment to use the FloorScore brand and logo.

SCS Global Services is a third-party certification firm that tests and verifies environmental, sustainability, and quality performance claims for various industries' products.

Therefore, to determine whether a product qualifies for the FloorScore seal, SCS Global Services will:

- Reviews all of the VOC emission test reports produced by independent testing laboratories for that product.
- Determines whether the test results meet the VOC requirements of Indoor Air Comfort in Europe or to California Section 01350.
- Conducts regular inspections of manufacturing plants to review formulas, processing, and quality control standards to maintain the integrity of the FloorScore® seal.

The certification process steps are as follows:

1. Application for Certification
Client submits Application Form. The certification body (CB) scopes the project and prepares a proposal which includes a detailed explanation of process, deliverables, cost, and timeline.
2. Data Collection
An auditor will work with client to collect product data and quality management documents. Once sufficient data is collected, an onsite audit is scheduled.
3. Onsite Audit
The CB auditor conducts an onsite audit, observing client's operation and interacting with technical staff to obtain any additional information needed. Auditor collects product sample for testing.
4. Product Testing

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A product is submitted to an CB-approved independent lab for emissions testing to the acceptable limits (depend on the region, e.g., for the US it is California 01350 standard, for the EU countries the limits are given by Directive 2008/50/EC which introduced additional PM2.5 objectives). Emissions test results can take approximately 3-4 weeks.

5. Audit Results

Auditor issues audit findings, if any are required. a Non-Conformance Report for any non-conformities observed.. Client responds to audit findings (if required).

6. Reporting

Auditor prepares Assessment Report detailing the audit findings, including data analysis, non-conformities, and opportunities for improvement.

7. Certification Decision

A CB reviewer conducts a final review of the draft Assessment Report and makes the certification decision. Client is listed in SCS Green Products Guide, and is granted the right to use the approved FloorScore® logo, consistent with SCS guidelines. SCS can also provide client marketing support.

8. Certification Maintenance and Renewal

Annual desk reviews of the quality system and product performance are required and are conducted to maintain certification. Any renewal testing required will be confirmed by the auditor during the evaluation process.

4.5.2 Nordic Swan Ecolabel

The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is an environmental labelling scheme certifying that a product or service complies with the requirements for the label.

The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is one of the most comprehensive and rigorous product certifications in the world. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel criteria set requirements for, for example, the content and use of environmentally hazardous chemicals, emissions to air, water and land, energy and resource use and waste management. The label also places demand on good quality and function. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel offers:

- A recipe on how to reduce the environmental impact from production and consumption of goods.
- A credible, third party certified guidance for their consumers and professional buyers to choose goods and services that are among the environmentally best.

The Nordic Swan Ecolabel was established in 1989 by The Nordic Council of Ministers as a voluntary eco-labelling scheme for the Nordic countries Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden. Today, it is the official ecolabel of the Nordic countries, supported by all Nordic governments and the most recognised environmental label in the region.

The goal is to enable consumers and professional buyers to choose the environmentally best goods and services by giving an effective tool to help companies develop more sustainable products and services.

The most important product group for the BIOBUILD project is Floor coverings 029. The product group includes floor coverings intended for indoors use as well as flooring underlays based on wood, cork, bamboo, laminate, linoleum, and PVC-free plastic raw materials.

A Nordic Swan Ecolabel floor covering or flooring underlay has reduced environmental impact throughout its lifecycle. The requirements span from renewable and/or recycled materials to chemicals and energy consumption. There is also a focus on circular aspects such as quality, traceability, warranty, reparability and recyclability. The requirements include:

- Use of a high proportion of renewable and/or recycled materials.
- Environmental and health properties of chemicals both used in manufacturing and added to the materials.
- Limits for energy use during manufacturing.
- Limits on emissions from formaldehyde and VOC in the final product.
- Test of the quality and performance.
- A 5-year warranty.

- Traceability to the manufacturer to ensure refurbishment, repair or recycling.

4.5.3 Cradle to cradle certification (C2C)

The Cradle to Cradle philosophy started in 2002 with the book 'Cradle to Cradle: Remaking the Way We Make Things' written by William McDonough and Michael Braungart (MBDC, 2014). Cradle to Cradle is elaborated from the idea that natural resources are exhaustible. Until now we live in a consumptive society, without caring about what will happen with our waste. We take out resources, we make something of it and we throw away the rests.

Sustainable design is about reuse, reduce and recycle for doing less badly. Sustainability does not consider the total life cycle of a product, such as the production process does. The Cradle to Cradle concept means doing '100% good', effective use of materials and consideration of the total life cycle of a product. Important in the C2C philosophy is that materials do not decrease in quality during their life cycle and could even improve in quality.

The concept is based on 3 basic ideas:

1. Waste = Food; so keep all materials in the biological or technical cycle.
2. Use only renewable energy, such as from the solar, wind and water.
3. Respect diversity; make sure that the material/product adds something to the nature environment [24].

Cradle to Cradle certification attempts to assess the environmental and social sustainability of goods in five categories: material health, material reutilization, renewable energy & carbon management, water stewardship, and social fairness. It applies only to physical products, but also considers aspects of how the producer does business, beyond the physical product. It is most applicable to products with only a few ingredients, such as furniture, food, clothing, or building materials.

Cradle to Cradle® certification follows a four-step process to assess products against five criteria:

- Material health: do the materials harm people or the environment?
- Material reutilisation: can the product and its parts be recycled or composted?
- Water stewardship: are the producer conserving water and discharging effluent wisely?
- Renewable electricity and carbon management: are the producer using renewable electricity and reducing carbon emissions?
- Social fairness: are you contributing positively to people and communities?
- Cradle to Cradle considers the flow of materials in two cycle: biological and technical.

Figure 13. Cradle to Cradle cycle of materials

There are the five levels of certification – basic, bronze, silver, gold and platinum.

Designing circular buildings using Cradle to Cradle Certified® (C2C) precepts requires a combination of two complementary approaches namely, material selection and building design. The first approach is to select building materials evaluated according to C2C certification criteria, such as non-toxicity of materials, end-of-life

reuse and recycling, and use of renewable energy. By choosing C2C-certified materials, companies ensure that the building is constructed with environmentally friendly materials that can be reused or recycled at the end of its life.

The second approach is to design the building in a circular way using the C2C inspired building benchmark. This approach evaluates buildings according to C2C criteria, but not only according to the materials used. Buildings that meet these criteria can be listed in a "C2C-inspired" building registry, which ensures that the building is designed to be sustainable and environmentally friendly. By applying these two approaches, companies can create buildings that are both circular, environmentally friendly and economically viable.

4.5.4 Blue Angel Ecolabel

The Blue Angel has been the ecolabel of the German Federal Government for more than 45 years. It is an independent and credible label that sets stringent standards for environmentally friendly products and services. The Blue Angel is a guide for purchasing.

The Blue Angel is an environmental label in Germany that has been awarded to particularly environmentally friendly products and services since 1978. The owner of the label is the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection.

It was established with the aim of highlighting more environmentally friendly and healthy developments and alternatives in areas where standard products have a negative impact on the environment. Suppliers can label their products and services with the environmental label

on a voluntary basis and provide interested customers with guidance as a result. The Blue Angel is thus a market-based, voluntary tool of environmental policy.

The Blue Angel guarantees that a product places less burden on the environment and fulfils high standards with respect to the protection of human health – while also having the same fitness for use and quality as other products. The Blue Angel only certifies the best products in a particular product group. The criteria are developed by the German Environment Agency on a scientific basis.

The Blue Angel is a so-called "Type I environmental label" according to DIN EN ISO 14024. This means that the entire life cycle of the product is taken into account and any impacts on the environment and health are fully considered during the development of the criteria ("multi-criteria evaluation"). In addition, the criteria are developed in a transparent process that includes both the suppliers affected as well as interested organisations within civil society and research institutions. Last but not least, the certification process is carried out by an independent body. The Blue Angel is a member of the international network of Type I ecolabels – the Global Ecolabelling Network (GEN) – which currently comprises 29 ecolabels from various nations.

The Blue Angel is not a label that certifies that a product is completely harmless. The products labelled with the Blue Angel are more environmentally friendly and healthier than other products that have the same fitness for use and quality in the respective product group. Therefore, these products represent the "lesser evil" with respect to environmental pollution in line with the motto: as little as possible, as much as necessary.

Specific requirements are defined for each product group. This means that those criteria that are relevant for the respective product group / service are selected from a broad range of possible criteria. The criteria and methods used to verify compliance with them are continually examined and updated. The aim is to define criteria in such a way that the best products on the market are able to fulfil them and companies within the sector are thus encouraged to further develop their products.

The following aspects are analysed during the development of the criteria:

- Resource-conserving production (water, energy, (recycled) materials).
- Sustainable production of raw materials.
- Avoidance of pollutants in products.
- Reduced emissions of harmful substances into the soil, air, water and indoor spaces.
- Reduction of noise and electromagnetic radiation.
- Efficient use and products that use a low level of energy or water.

- Durability, reparability and recyclability.
- Good fitness for use.
- Observance of international standards for occupational safety.
- Return systems and services that enable the common use of products such as car sharing.

All of the criteria for the award of the environmental label to the individual product groups are published on the Blue Angel website in a transparent way. The independent certification body – RAL gGmbH – ensures that the certified products and services comply with the relevant criteria.

4.6 The Environmental Product Declaration (EPD)

An Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) is a transparent, objective report that communicates product content and environmental impacts across a product or product category life cycle. EPDs are standardised life cycle assessments (LCAs) based on the ISO 14040 Standard series, EN 15804 and a Type III Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) that is compliant with ISO 14025 Standard and is third party verified. An EPD is utilized by specifiers to better understand environmental impacts of a product and to comply with material requirements in building rating systems.

An EPD is a document in which the environmentally-relevant properties of a product are outlined in the form of neutral and objective data. This data covers as many impacts as possible which the product can have on its environment, whereby in an ideal situation, the entire life cycle of the product is taken into consideration.

In the area of construction, EPDs represent an essential basis for experts such as architects and planners when it comes to the comprehensive planning and evaluation of buildings. But EPDs are not suitable for direct comparisons of products as the degree of environmental friendliness, conservation of resources or sustainability displayed by a construction product is largely dependent on the (building) context in which it is used. EN 19978 provides guidelines on how to incorporate EPDs for an evaluation on a building level.

EPDs do not simply contain random estimates or arbitrary numbers. They are based on life cycle assessments of construction products. A life cycle assessment summarises and analyses the environmental impacts of a certain product across its life cycle, from the provision of raw materials to the finished product ready for installation. Processes and factors associated with the product are also taken into consideration, e.g. packaging and transport. Increasingly, other phases of the life cycle are also considered, e.g., use phase, recycling, reuse and disposal.

One particularly important feature of life cycle assessments is the fact that they do not deliver a single parameter or assessment but rather individually depict a variety of different environmental influences. For example, apart from greenhouse gas emissions, other influencing factors such as acid rain, smog formation, consumption of fossil resources and water or recycling percentages are also considered. All this information is included in EPDs which means that it is publicly available – after all, truly sustainable solutions can only be found by simultaneously considering as many environmental impacts as possible.

EPDs have become increasingly crucial in the construction industry. This is because they enable facile comparison between the environmental impacts of similar materials and components used. Therefore, enabling sustainable building practices whilst also reducing barriers around verification and sourcing. This empowers architects, engineers, and designers to select the most sustainable options for their projects, while also enabling manufacturers to optimise the environmental impacts of their products and effectively communicate their commitment to environmental transparency.

The first step in creating an EPD is defining the product, using the appropriate Product Category Rules (PCR). A Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the LCA must be verified and from reliable sources (for example, from a manufacturing facility). A Life Cycle Environmental Impact Analysis (LCIA) is performed by an LCA expert using software and a variety of assessment tools. The EPD is delivered as a document or report following a series of verification reviews; it is then ready for registration and publication.

The EPD is generally valid for five years and is based on international standards from above (ISO 14040, ISO14044, and ISO 14025). In the building products industry, EPD is based on EN 15804 too. EPD and LCA

also serve as the basis for building sustainability schemes such as LEED¹¹, BREEAM¹², Living Building Challenge¹³, and DGNB¹⁴.

Through life cycle assessment, the manufacturer could better analyse and optimize the production technology and raw materials used to reduce the product's impact on the environment, improving sustainability and competitiveness. The EPD development process is depicted in Figure 14 and has several steps.

- **Step 1: Selecting the EPD Program Operator (EPD PO).**
The first step in creating an EPD is to identify the appropriate EPD Program Operator (EPD PO) based on factors such as geographical relevance, cost considerations, and mutual recognition agreements between EPD POs. This decision is crucial, as the selected EPD PO will determine the specific requirements and guidelines that must be followed.
- **Step 2: Identifying the Relevant Product Category Rule (PCR).**
Once the EPD PO has been selected, the next step is to identify the appropriate Product Category Rule (PCR) that aligns with the characteristics of the product. The EPD PO can often provide guidance and support in this process, ensuring that the selected PCR meets the requirements.
- **Step 3: Conducting the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).**
With the PCR in place, the manufacturer can proceed to conduct a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the product, adhering to the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards. This LCA forms the foundation of the EPD, providing the detailed environmental impact data that will be presented in the final document.
- **Step 4: Engaging a Third-Party Verifier & Drafting EPD Document.**
A crucial step in the EPD creation process is the involvement of an independent, third-party verifier. This verifier, recognised by the selected EPD PO, reviews the LCA report and the EPD document to ensure compliance with the relevant standards, PCR, and verification protocols.
Following the third-party verification, the manufacturer can then proceed to draft the EPD document, following the format and requirements prescribed by the chosen EPD PO. This includes incorporating the LCA results, a brief product description, the assumptions made throughout the LCA, and the calculation rules employed (i.e., the PCR).
- **Step 5: Submitting the Verified EPD.**
The final step in the process is to submit the verified EPD to the EPD Program Operator for publication on platforms connected to the ECO Platform¹⁵, a prominent EPD umbrella organisation. This completes the EPD creation journey, ensuring that the product's environmental impact information is made publicly available and accessible to stakeholders.

¹¹ The LEED® rating system, used in USA has seven areas of concentration; Sustainable Sites, Water Efficiency, Energy and Atmosphere, Materials and Resources, Indoor Environmental Quality, Innovation in Design Process and Regional Priority. Projects obtain credits in these areas to achieve certification. A building becomes certified after receiving a minimum of 40 credits from the USGBC (United States Green Building Council).

¹² A BREEAM certified rating (initially also from USA, but today with branches all around the globe) reflects the performance achieved by a project and its stakeholders, as measured against the BREEAM standard and its benchmarks. The BREEAM ratings range from Acceptable (In-Use scheme only) to Pass, Good, Very Good, Excellent to Outstanding and it is reflected in a series of stars on the BREEAM certificate.

¹³ According to the International Living Future Institute, "as such the program is a Philosophy first, an advocacy tool second, and a certification program third ... Living Buildings strive for net-zero or net-positive energy, are free of toxic chemicals, and lower their energy footprint many times below the generic commercial structure."

The Living Building Challenge sets stringent requirements particularly in terms of water, energy and waste, where buildings are required to achieve a net zero or net positive balance. The requirements in terms of place, health and happiness, equity and beauty are somewhat less difficult to achieve.

¹⁴ First launched in a pilot phase in 2008, the DGNB system is a relative newcomer among the comprehensive building rating systems. Its criteria were initially developed by the German Sustainable Building Council together with the German Ministry of Construction. DGNB is also being applied internationally. DGNB has separate schemes for existing buildings, refurbished buildings and the management of existing buildings.

¹⁵ The ECO Platform is the umbrella organisation of the various national EPD program operators in Europe, and supports the creation of a European Core EPD system based on the EN 15804 European standard. The European program operators involved have agreed upon certain minimum standards in relation to quality management and the verification procedure, whose observance they have obligated themselves to. EPDs that carry the ECO Platform EPD logo and are listed on the ECO Platform stand for the best possible comparability to date in terms of a coordinated European solution.

The ECO Platform initiative, which is the basis for the creation of international recognition, has been well-received in the industry. Along with IBU, as program operator in Germany, the founding members of the ECO Platform also include the European building materials association Construction Products Europe.

Figure 14. The most common EPD framework [25]

5 Conclusion and recommendations for BIOBUILD project

The overall objectives of the BIOBUILD project are important to the future adaptation to climate change of residential and office building in the EU, and this has resulted in a strong commitment by partners involved to drive the execution of the project. In this regard, there is a high likelihood of sustainability of project activities, and the future of the project is well grounded in the EU development and policy.

Buildings have a considerable environmental impact that corresponds to almost 30% of the global carbon footprint, with a prediction for future growth and 40% of energy consumption in the EU. Since 2002, the European Commission has established a common policy for sustainable buildings and low environmental impact materials promoting energy efficiency and reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG), based on a series of directives and regulations.

The market for construction materials offers vast potentials, but it also presents significant challenges. One of the major driving forces is the growing demand for sustainable construction materials. Consumers are increasingly seeking out environmentally friendly options and are demanding credible evidence of sustainable production processes and materials.

Manufacturers and retailers aiming to access international markets must navigate a complex landscape of legal requirements. The "Construction Products Regulation" (CPR) plays a crucial role in this regard. Harmonized standards covered by the CPR state precise requirements for the product and provide guidance for evaluating construction products. This regulation is particularly noteworthy as it forms the foundation for successfully entering the lucrative EU market. Conforming to the CPR is an essential prerequisite for obtaining the CE marks, demonstrating compliance with the regulatory standards.

On the other hand, the "Sustainable buildings' management" is a complex problem which needs effective, adequate and suitable assessment tools and methods to address issues of incommensurability and complexity, always considering the prevailing environmental policies and legislation.

The environmental certification processes promote environmental evaluation aspects relevant to the building's life cycle, as an expression of the overall legislative framework for sustainable management of buildings. Therefore, and aiming to improve the energy efficiency in the overall life cycle of buildings, emphasis must be given to the materials' selection, focusing on low environmental impact during the production process and the use of natural, recyclable or recycled materials, originating ideally locally, so as to minimise energy consumed for transportation and the resulting emissions.

The fact that construction materials contribute in a most decisive way to sustainable building management has been proven by many studies; the construction materials are therefore highly important elements for the energy conscious and bioclimatic design and construction of the new buildings.

Taking into consideration the ongoing economic recession that affects the construction sector in many European countries, but also the energy poverty that makes significant part of the population to suffer, it is reasonable to expect that sustainability and therefore construction products certification, mostly green certification cannot be among the top priorities for many businesses and organizations. However, there is also evidence that environmental management and implementing sustainability policies in the construction products helps in reducing energy and raw materials use, and can therefore lead to a cleaner and more cost-efficient production. The above is the reason for the continual increase of the issued certificates. Sustainability remains essential basically for two reasons, i.e., the improvement of the quality of living and the marketing of systems and products.

The following recommendations emerged out of the discussions with WP1 partners and aimed to provide guidance for the implementation of the project:

- The certification process includes an inspection and/or full review of the aspect that is being certified. It may also include an assessment of associated paperwork to make sure that it is accurate. Having that certification

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means that the independent party has deemed that the organisation, facility, product, system, service or process complies with specific quality, performance and safety standards. For flooring and wallboard products, third party certification is often recommended as an addition to a declaration of conformity (DOC) or declaration of performance (DOP).

- Independent, third-party certification helps a manufacturer or economic operator to distinguish themselves from other suppliers by offering a higher level of assurance that the product, system or service they are supplying meets the relevant safety, quality and performance regulations.
 - By obtaining a third-party certification, manufacturers demonstrate a higher level of care, which allows their products to be more quickly accepted into the marketplace.
 - For the consumers, a third-party certification means that they can purchase a product with more confidence and be assured that a handling system is in place to identify unsafe products and prohibit or remove them from being sold in the marketplace.
 - For the specifiers, a third-party certification provides reassurance that the products they select have been tested to industry standards – whether it is the whole product or a key product characteristic – and the product will perform as stated when installed or fitted as instructed.
- Construction products certification is an indispensable aspect of modern business operations. It ensures that products are safe, reliable, and of high quality, contributing to consumer trust and regulatory compliance.
- It's important to note that certification requirements can vary depending on the type of product, its intended use, and the specific regulations in place at any given time.
- From the producers' point of view, it should also be taken into account the fact that at the moment there are several competing certification schemes, at the level of a country, (and at the level of the EU) which practically certify the same type of product, from the point of view of the system of manufacture, or as the ecological label of the product etc. This can create confusion among users of the product. It would be desirable, at least at the level of the single European market, to have a clearer "standardization" of the certification schemes.

Direct recommendations to the BIOBUILD project:

- A number of Eurocodes must be considered because they provide important information concerning the products that should be developed in the project. Important material characteristics found in the Eurocodes are the limits of the floor frequencies caused by human-induced vibrations. Eurocode 5 provides the guidelines for timber structure design, in particular the use of wood-based panels and softboards. Requirements about the strength of the adhesives as well as the natural durability of wood and wood-based materials found in the Eurocodes must be considered in the process of research and development of the new products.
- Regarding the forest certification, there are two main options namely, FSC and PEFC. The novel building products must demonstrate that the employed wood materials originate from responsibly managed forests that provides environmental, social and economic benefits. In the project, it is desirable and enough to prove that the wood material comes from certified forests.
- Using fatty acid mixtures, unstudied esters in the construction products will need some test and even certification regarding, toxicity, sustainability, and natural availability. In this context probably a Floor Score certificate or another environmental ecolabel will be a good starting point from the point of view of a consumer protection.
- Using of plant oils as starting material to synthesize non-toxic bio-resins is a correct beginning from the point of view of toxicity and environment, but future products may need quality certification to demonstrate the viability and durability of the products.
- Using LCA and LCC analyses for the new building materials proposed in the BIOBUILD project will be a very good starting point, but will these analyses be enough for the future end users? We must take in consideration that the future products could have a better start if we adopt a certification scheme from the very beginning.
- Special attention should be paid to the certification of the novel products developed in the project in a later phase when the certification could be demanded by the stakeholders.

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